

HyDelta 3

WP1b – Asset Management – Repurposing Offshore Infrastructure

D1b.2 Repurposing protocol

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Document summary

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- Activities (e.g. maintenance, purging etc.)
- Assets
- Digitalisation
- End use
- Gas network
- QRA

Social aspects

- Conversion (of the distribution network)
- Education
- Social

System and Economy

- Business Development
- Production and supply
- Value chains

Gas Quality

- Admixing
- Gas Quality
- Odourisation

Executive summary

Existing North Sea pipeline infrastructure has been designed for transporting natural gas. As oil and gas activities decline, North Sea pipelines and platforms can be repurposed for hydrogen production and distribution. By converting excess renewable electricity from offshore wind farms into hydrogen through electrolysis, existing gas pipelines can transport this clean energy source. Therefore, there is a critical need to develop specific guidelines and standards for the safe and efficient repurposing of offshore natural gas pipelines for hydrogen transport.

Reusing offshore infrastructure for hydrogen service presents several challenges. One of the primary issues is the lack of a universally accepted design standard for hydrogen transport in offshore pipelines. While design codes such as the NEN 3650 series, ASME B31.12 (soon to be merged into ASME B31.8), and DVGW G409 and G464 exist for land-based pipelines, they cannot be directly applied to offshore pipelines due to the unique environmental loads and conditions these structures face.

To address this gap, DNV is currently developing a recommended practice, DNV RP-F123 "Design and Operation of Hydrogen Pipelines." This guideline aims to provide a comprehensive framework for the safe and reliable design, construction, operation and re-qualification, of pipelines dedicated to hydrogen gas transportation.

As part of this effort, this report provides a detailed protocol based on the latest DNV service specification, DNV-SE-0657. The purpose of DNV-SE-0657 is to establish a consistent approach and methodology for re-qualifying pipeline systems intended for CO₂ and hydrogen transport. The proposed re-qualification process involves a series of compliance checks and assessments designed to ensure that pipeline systems meet current safety, regulatory, and operational standards.

Samenvatting

De leidinginfrastructuur in de Noordzee is oorspronkelijk ontworpen voor het transport van aardgas en wordt gereguleerd door een reeks industriële standaarden en lokale voorschriften die de constructie en operatie van deze systemen beheren. Het hergebruik van offshore-infrastructuur voor waterstoftransport vormt verschillende technische uitdagingen. Een van de belangrijkste kwesties is het ontbreken van ontwerpnormen voor waterstoftransport in offshore-pijpleidingen. Hoewel er ontwerpcodes bestaan, zoals de NEN 3650-serie, ASME B31.12 (binnenkort samengevoegd met ASME B31.8) en DVGW G409 en G464 voor landgebonden pijpleidingen, kunnen deze niet direct worden toegepast op offshore-pijpleidingen vanwege de unieke operationele omstandigheden waaraan deze structuren blootstaan.

Om dit probleem aan te pakken, ontwikkelt DNV momenteel DNV RP-F123 "Design and Operation of Hydrogen Pipelines." Dit document is bedoeld om een holistisch kader te bieden voor het veilige, betrouwbare ontwerp, de constructie, de exploitatie en de herkwalificatie van pijpleidingen die specifiek bestemd zijn voor waterstoftransport.

Als onderdeel van deze ontwikkeling presenteert dit rapport een gedetailleerd protocol op basis van de meest recente servicespecificatie DNV-SE-0657. Het voorgestelde herkwalificatieproces omvat een reeks compliance-controles en beoordelingen die ervoor zorgen dat pijpleidingsystemen voldoen aan de geldende veiligheidsnormen, regelgeving en operationele eisen.

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1. Introduction

On May 18th, 2022, the Energy ministers of Belgium, Denmark, Germany, and the Netherlands signed the declaration on the North Sea as a Green Power Plant of Europe, commonly referred to as the Esbjerg Declaration. Building on this momentum, the Ostend Declaration, introduced in 2024, represents a major expansion of this vision. In the Ostend Declaration, a coalition of nine countries—Belgium, Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands, as well as France, Ireland, Luxembourg, Norway, and Sweden—committed to transform the North Sea into the world’s largest green energy power plant. This expanded coalition aims to further accelerate the development of offshore wind energy and strengthen cross-border energy integration, driving significant advancements toward a sustainable and integrated energy system in the North Sea region.

The Declaration supports Europe in switching from fossil energy to renewable energy derived from the North Sea area and has set ambitious combined targets for offshore wind of at least 120 GW by 2030 in the North Seas. Based on the North Sea as a Green Power Plant of Europe, together we aim to more than double our total 2030-capacity of offshore wind to at least 300 GW by 2050.

Hydrogen from the North Sea, in which green hydrogen is produced offshore from wind energy and brought ashore via hydrogen pipelines, should help to unlock the enormous potential of energy production on the North Sea. To realize this potential an offshore hydrogen infrastructure is needed. Most probably Gasunie will be appointed by the Dutch Government to develop a hydrogen network at the North Sea. The development of this infrastructure will be partly based on re-using existing offshore natural gas infrastructure.

There are a significant number of publications and press releases in the public domain claiming that onshore pipeline networks are ready to transport hydrogen and that existing infrastructure is suitable for re-purposing. This information notwithstanding, for offshore pipelines some additional failure modes are still conceivable. Also, the effect of the pipeline transport characteristics on the quality of the hydrogen is still an open question. This explains why there is intensive work ongoing in several research programs in the industry to close those offshore transport knowledge gaps (TNO [1], IOGP [2]). Both projects have the character of a techno-economic feasibility study, however, do not go into detail on the specific issues related to re-use of existing gas pipelines.

In this HyDelta research project the focus is on the re-qualification of existing offshore pipelines to ensure a reliable infrastructure.

2. Scope of Work

The North Sea's pipeline infrastructure, originally intended for natural gas transport, is governed by industry standards and local regulations. Current guidelines offer minimal insight into modifying existing pipelines for hydrogen transport. Claims of readiness to use these natural gas pipelines for hydrogen are based on preliminary evaluations using ASME B31.12, a standard tailored for onshore, pipelines. Off-shore pipelines could face unique failures that are not addressed in the ASME B31.12, such as from dynamic stresses and buckling. There is a pressing need for more detailed criteria for off-repurposing off-shore pipelines for hydrogen service. So, it is important to establish offshore pipeline requalification protocol, which will provide:

- An overview of the specifications/conditions/characteristics/properties that would need to apply to a re-design/re-qualification of offshore hydrogen pipelines (Not everything is known and/or documented about this)- literature review and interviews with pipeline experts globally

- More insight in which requirements these pipelines should meet (e.g. regarding free span, dynamic loads, fatigue, buckling, etc.).

Furthermore, the protocol shall refer to DNV's H2Pipe project and other relevant offshore pipeline projects.

The scope of work is to understand the potential offshore specific challenges when converting them to hydrogen and define approach how to convert such pipelines

Activities:

- Desk research
- Literature review
- Workshops with DNV experts
- Establish offshore pipeline requalification protocol

2.1 Assumptions

- The offshore pipelines were previously in upstream natural gas service. Pipelines in oil service are not in scope.
- This study is to cover the steps needed to be taken to convert existing offshore pipeline to hydrogen service
- This study will not be specific for one specific pipeline, but a generic approach for an upstream offshore gas pipelines in the Netherlands.
- Flexible risers and other non-ferrous components are not in scope.

3. Background

The Dutch government plans to develop energy hubs in the North Sea beyond 2030, which will enable the production and transportation of electricity and hydrogen to the shore of the country and neighboring countries. The energy hubs will include the production of green hydrogen at sea and pipelines to transport hydrogen to shore [3]. With traditional oil and gas activities decreasing, the North Sea's network of pipelines and platforms can be repurposed for another service. One of the most exciting possibilities is producing and distributing hydrogen. By converting excess renewable electricity from offshore wind farms into hydrogen through a process called electrolysis, the existing gas pipelines can be used to transport this clean energy source. The International North Sea Energy Atlas provides an overview of existing infrastructure at the North Sea [4].

Figure 1 – The North Sea Energy Atlas

Considering the forecasted development of energy hubs in the North Sea, Table 1 provides a comprehensive inventory of pipelines earmarked for repurposing.

Table 1 – Inventory of identified pipeline potentially attractive to transport hydrogen [1]

Pipe segment	Operator	NPS (inches)	Duty	From	To
PLR0099_PR	TAQA	26	Gas	P15-D	Maasvlakte
PL0223_PR	Neptune	8	Gas	Q16-FA-1	Maasvlakte
PL0138_PR	NAM	8	Gas	Q16-FA-1	P18-A
PL0106_PR	TAQA	16	Gas	P18-A	P15-D
PL0030_PR	NAM	24	Gas	K15-FB-1	LOCAL
PL0004_PR	Wintershall	36	Gas	K13-AP	WGT
PL0091_PR	Neptune	24	Gas	L2-FA-1	NOGAT
PL0061_PR	Wintershall	10.7	Gas	Q8-A	Ijmuiden
PL0218_PR	Wintershall	10	Gas	Q4-C	Q8-A
PL0003_PR	Noordgastransport	36	Gas	L10-AR	NGT
PL0142_PR	Noordgastransport	36	Gas	D15-FA-1	L10-AC

The offshore pipelines in the Dutch North Sea have been developed from the 1970's up to the late 1990's and designed for transport of natural gas according to NEN 3656 or a previously accepted historical standard. In general, they are made of carbon steel grades X42 through to X70, with seam welds. This is in line with the typical materials selected in European countries at the time. Outer diameters vary per segment, whereas the schedule is typically XS or thicker (> 12.7 mm) [1].

Many of the pipelines in the Dutch North Sea have exceeded their original design life, presenting significant challenges related to structural integrity and operational reliability. Key concerns include increased susceptibility to fatigue damage, compliance with evolving burial requirements, deterioration of coating materials, and potential internal and external corrosion. Aging infrastructure is also more prone to incidents during repair and maintenance, amplifying operational risks.

Moreover, the non-destructive testing (NDT) techniques available for older pipelines often lack the precision and resolution of modern methods, resulting in less reliable assessments of their condition compared to newer pipelines. These factors make the repurposing of existing pipelines a more complex and technically demanding endeavor than the construction of new ones.

The reuse of offshore infrastructure for hydrogen service presents several challenges. Currently, there is no widely accepted design standard for hydrogen transport in offshore pipelines. While design codes such as the NEN 3650 series, ASME B31.12 (soon to be merged into ASME B31.8), DVGW G409, and G464 exist for land pipelines, they cannot be directly applied to offshore pipelines due to the unique loads encountered in these environments.

ASME B31.12 is frequently used as a template for repurposing assessments, but the requirements for hydrogen service are difficult to meet for existing pipelines. This highlights the need for clear guidelines to support Dutch North Sea operators in the repurposing process. It is important to note that ASME B31.12 primarily focuses on onshore applications, whereas offshore pipelines have distinct challenges.

To address these gaps, DNV is leading the JIP H2Pipe initiative, which aims to develop clearer guidance and establish more accurate and reliable requirements for hydrogen pipelines. This initiative also seeks to deepen understanding of the design limitations, ensuring safer and more effective pipeline repurposing and development for hydrogen service.

As part of the North Sea Energy Infrastructure Plan, Gasunie has prepared a comprehensive memo to assist pipeline owners and consultants in making well-structured and informed decisions on this topic. It outlines the criteria that Gasunie, as the Hydrogen Network Operator, will assess to determine the suitability of an existing pipeline for hydrogen transport. The memo is set to be incorporated as Appendix S in the NEN 3656 standard, ensuring its alignment with established guidelines and enhancing its accessibility within the regulatory framework [5].

4. Subsea Pipeline Safety Regulations in the Netherlands

The safety regulations governing subsea pipelines in the Netherlands are based on a combination of national laws, European Union (EU) directives, and international standards. These regulations are designed to ensure the safe design, construction, operation, and decommissioning of subsea pipelines. These regulations should be consulted when repurposing an existing pipeline/riser from natural gas to hydrogen. A key component of these safety regulations is the requirement for operators to maintain comprehensive emergency response plans. These plans are crucial for effectively addressing incidents such as leaks or ruptures. These plans must include:

- Immediate containment and mitigation strategies
- Coordination with emergency services and the Dutch Coast Guard
- Environmental clean-up operations if a spill occurs

Review and update of emergency response plans will need to occur if pipelines are repurposed for hydrogen. Implementation of revised plans will require new drills to be formulated and practiced regularly.

It shall be noted that in the case of offshore hydrogen pipelines, the regulatory framework is not yet formally established. These pipelines are expected to fall outside the scope of the Mining Act, suggesting that State Supervision of Mines (SODM) may not act as the regulatory body. Instead, regulatory oversight is anticipated to fall under Rijkswaterstaat (RWS), which has currently assumed informal responsibility. However, the formal designation of the responsible authority remains pending and is to be determined by the Ministry of Climate and Energy Policy (KGG, formerly EZK). RWS, in the interim, provides advisory support to the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, highlighting the need for a definitive governance framework to support the safe and efficient transition to hydrogen infrastructure.

Below is an overview of the key subsea pipeline safety regulations applicable in the Netherlands.

4.1 Dutch Mining Act (Mijnbouwwet)

The Mining Act is the primary national legislation governing the exploration and extraction of minerals, including oil and gas, and it extends to the safety of associated infrastructure including subsea pipelines. It mandates the safe design, construction, operation, and maintenance of subsea pipelines to minimise risks to people, property, and the environment. Operators must ensure the integrity of pipelines throughout their lifecycle, conducting regular safety inspections and risk assessments. The State Supervision of Mines (SodM) is the primary enforcement body under the Mining Act.

4.1.1 Dutch Mining Regulations (Mijnbouwregeling)

The Mining Regulations provide specific technical and safety rules for activities regulated under the Mining Act. For subsea pipelines, this includes requirements for:

- Pipeline design and construction standards
- Risk assessments and safety plans before pipeline installation
- Monitoring and inspection throughout the pipeline's operational life
- Emergency response plan in case of leaks, ruptures, or other incidents
- Pipeline Integrity Management: These regulations require operators to implement integrity management systems that regularly assess the structural condition of subsea pipelines, ensuring their continued safety and compliance with standards.

4.1.2 State Supervision of Mines (Staatstoezicht op de Mijnen - SodM)

Provision of Regulatory Oversight: SodM is responsible for ensuring compliance with subsea pipeline safety regulations. It oversees inspections, audits, and risk assessments and has the authority to issue penalties for non-compliance. Incident Reporting and Investigation: SodM also oversees the reporting of pipeline incidents, investigating leaks, failures, or accidents, and recommending improvements to safety practices when necessary.

4.2 National Dutch Standards

These national Dutch standards provide the minimum standards for pipeline design, operation and safety and are applicable for hydrogen:

- NEN-3656:2022 Requirements for Submarine Steel Pipeline Systems, March 2022
- NEN-3650-1:2020 Requirements for pipeline systems - Part 1: General Requirements
- NEN-3650-2:2020 Requirements for pipeline systems – Part 2: Additional specifications for steel pipelines
- NEN-3651:2020 Additional requirements for pipelines in or nearby important public works
- NEN-EN 14161:2011+A2015 Petroleum and natural gas industries - Pipeline transportation systems

4.2.1 NEN3656:2022 Requirements for Submarine Steel Pipeline Systems

NEN-3656: specifies the requirements for quantified risk assessment required for a hydrogen pipeline, this is detailed in the below section.

The standard provides minimum requirements relating to safety aspects for people, the environment and property for the construction, installation, commissioning and decommissioning and operational management of submarine pipeline systems for the transport of substances. It specifically states:

*“This standard may be used in support for pipeline systems which are used in renewable energy applications, such as **hydrogen**, ammonia and carbon dioxide. However, an additional risk assessment is then needed.”*

And:

*“The requirements are applicable for new submarine pipeline systems to be constructed or modification of existing submarine pipeline systems. Modification of existing systems means modification of process conditions (temperature, pressure, **fluid**)”*

The standard categorises both natural gas and hydrogen as Group I (intrinsically dangerous) and Extremely Flammable substances F⁺.

Section 6.7.2 of the standard describes the required safety level for persons at the pipeline landfall site in terms of local risk (LR) (individual risk) and group risk (GR). The levels of LR and GR are specified by Bevb [6]:

For the landfall site: $LR \leq 10^{-6}$ per year.

According to the Bevb, GR means: the cumulative risks per year per kilometre of pipeline that at least 10, 100 or 1,000 people will die as a direct consequence of their presence in the area of influence of a pipeline and an unusual event with this pipeline.

Area of influence here means the area in which people are taken into account for the calculation of the group risk of the pipeline up to the limit within which the fatality rate for these persons is 1%.

The guide value for the acceptable group risk is stated in Formula: $F \times N2 \leq 0.01$

where: F is the acceptable risk per year of the simultaneous death of N people.

Appendix D describes the requirements of the pipelines and riser Quantified Risk Assessment (QRA) at the landfall site and the offshore installation.

For offshore installations the 500-meter zone is regarded as the area with an increased risk of damage, within which the pipeline shall possibly be covered or other mitigating measures (e.g., mattresses) shall be taken. This should be reviewed in the light of potential higher atmospheric dispersion distances of subsea hydrogen pipeline releases (see Appendix 8).

4.3 European Union Directives

4.3.1 Offshore Safety Directive (2013/30/EU)

This EU directive sets standards for the safety of offshore oil and gas operations, including the infrastructure such as subsea pipelines. Operators must implement comprehensive safety and environmental management systems (SEMS) to prevent major accidents and ensure high safety standards for subsea pipelines.

Seveso III Directive (2012/18/EU)

This is applicable only where pipeline landfall is inside a site (e.g. a gas terminal) which falls under the onshore Seveso III Directive. It requires the operator to assess the risks associated with the site and develop an onsite and offsite emergency plan.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)

This directive focuses on the protection of the marine environment, indirectly influencing pipeline operations by requiring the prevention of pollution from pipelines and ensuring that offshore activities do not harm marine ecosystems.

Environment Management Act (Wet Milieubeheer)

This act sets out the general environmental management framework in the Netherlands, including measures to prevent environmental hazards from subsea pipelines. Operators must ensure that subsea pipelines do not lead to environmental degradation, particularly from oil or gas leaks.

Health and Safety Legislation - Working Conditions Act (Arbowet)

This law outlines workplace safety requirements, including those for personnel involved in the construction, operation, and maintenance of subsea pipelines. It mandates that all workers are provided with a safe working environment, proper training, and emergency response plans.

4.4 International Standards and Best Practices

4.4.1 ISO 13623:2017 (Pipeline Transportation Systems)

Operators in the Netherlands often follow this international standard, which provides guidelines for the design, construction, and operation of pipeline systems, including subsea infrastructure.

4.4.2 DNV Standards

DNV is a globally recognised provider of industry standards for subsea pipelines. These standards cover pipeline design, risk assessments, and integrity management and are widely adopted by Dutch operators to enhance safety compliance.

- DNV-ST-F101 - Submarine Pipeline Systems, Aug 2021 [7]- see Section 0 below for applicability for H₂.
- DNV-OS-A101 – Safety Principles and Arrangements, March 2023.

DNV Standard – DNV-ST-F101 Submarine Pipeline Systems

The standard requires a systematic review to be carried out at all phases to identify and evaluate threats, the consequences of single failures and series of failures in the pipeline system, such that necessary remedial measures can be taken. The extent of the review or analysis shall reflect the criticality of the pipeline system, the criticality of a planned operation, and previous experience with similar systems or operations. The uncertainty in the applied risk review model itself shall also be qualified. Special attention shall be given to sections close to installations or shore approaches where there is frequent human activity and thus a greater likelihood and consequence of damage to the pipeline. This also includes areas where pipelines are installed parallel to existing pipelines and pipeline crossings. The pipeline design philosophy for the offshore installation and shore approach and the onshore pipeline is defined by safety class which is determined by fluid category, location class, safety class and phase. The DNV standard is applicable for hydrogen pipelines. It categorises hydrogen as Category E – flammable and/or toxic. Natural gas pipelines would also be categorized as Category E. It shall be noted that the DNV standard requires to consider the effect of content on material properties, but it does not provide any guidance on this. For a given hydrogen pipeline, the safety class should be assessed (see sections 2.3.4 of DNV-ST-F101) to determine the nominal annual target failure probabilities per pipeline for different limit state categories e.g. ULS Ultimate Limit State the condition which, if exceeded, compromises the integrity of the pipeline.

Appendix F.2.2 of DNV-ST-F101 defines the safety philosophy for the shore approach and onshore pipeline sections. It implies that the consequences of failure (economical, environmental and human) shall be quantified by the concept of safety class. The safety class is determined by fluid category, location class and phase (construction, operation) of the pipeline. The presence of people and nearby onshore facilities necessitates a further refinement of the location classes used offshore. In highly populated areas the consequences may be more severe than for offshore, requiring a higher safety class, very high.

Currently, DNV is developing a recommended practice DNV RP-F123 “Design and operation of hydrogen pipelines” that will provide a guideline for safe and reliable design, re-qualification, construction and operation of pipelines intended for transportation of hydrogen gas [8].

5. Design Levels offshore pipelines

When repurposing existing offshore pipelines for hydrogen transport, it is important to thoroughly re-evaluate the design levels to ensure the pipeline can safely and efficiently accommodate hydrogen's unique properties. Repurposing offshore pipelines for hydrogen transport can introduce new load scenarios compared to the original design, such as changes in internal pressure, flow dynamics, and external environmental forces, requiring a comprehensive re-evaluation of design parameters. The design process is typically categorized into three levels—low, medium, and high—each suited to specific operational and environmental conditions:

- **Low Design Level:** Suitable for pipelines in shallow waters with even seabed conditions, minimal bending, and low-pressure environments. This level assumes a straightforward installation and limited environmental challenges.

- Medium Design Level: Designed for pipelines in moderate-depth waters with varying seabed conditions, moderate bending, and medium-pressure environments. It accounts for some environmental challenges and requires more robust materials and design considerations.
- Very High/High Design Level: Necessary for pipelines in deep-water environments with uneven seabed, significant bending, and exposure to harsh environmental conditions. This level addresses significant operational stresses, requiring advanced materials, sophisticated engineering, and comprehensive risk management.

For a low design level, a hydrogen environment will have less of an impact while high level design scenarios may not be feasible for operation with hydrogen.

Table 2 – Load scenarios [8], [9]

Load scenario ²	Stress component of concern ¹	Characterisation	Design level
Even seabed/onshore - low hoop stress	H + L	Low stress	Low
Even seabed/onshore - high hoop stress	H+ L	Stress based	Medium
Un-even seabed	L	Stress based	Medium
Commissioning/shut-downs	H + L	Stress based	Medium
Storage cycles	H + L	Low cycle fatigue	High
Accidental loads	H + L	Strain based	Very high
Global buckling	L	Strain based	Very high
1. L = longitudinal, H = Hoop/circumferential 2. In addition to affecting the mechanical stresses, the pressure level may also have an impact on the degradation of the mechanical properties.			

The challenges associated with each of the load scenarios are as follows:

- Even seabed/onshore - low hoop stress: Typical onshore pipeline with low pressure utilisation. Challenges related to fatigue of longitudinal weld and girth weld.
- Even seabed - high pressure: Typical offshore pipeline on even seabed. Larger challenges related to fatigue of longitudinal weld and girth weld.
- Un-even seabed: Additional challenges linked to
 - permanent bending on shoulders
 - permanent bending in free-spans. Variations in bending due to variations in pressure and/or temperature
 - VIV in free-spans, causing fatigue of girth welds
 - Direct wave and/or current loading causing movement of the pipeline
- Commissioning/shutdowns: Slowly increasing stresses may cause flaws to grow under lower effective crack resistance

- Storage cycles: Additional challenge caused by large stress cycles across longitudinal welds and girth welds.
- Accidental loads: Additional challenge caused significant local plastic strains due to third party interference. It is likely to have equivalent resistance to these as for normal natural gas pipelines, but the developed defects may become critical with time and lead to loss of containment with associated consequences unless mitigated.
- Global buckling: Additional challenges caused by cyclic, longitudinal strains typically beyond 0.5%. Such strain levels present a challenge both from high static load and cyclic loads.

6. Repurposing protocol

Key factors when evaluating the repurposing of pipelines for hydrogen transportation are categorized into environmental (hydrogen pressure, impurities, and temperature), material (grade, microstructure, and chemical composition), operations (pressure, loading variations, and residual stresses), and current state (weld quality, defects, and installation strain).

Re-qualification must be based on comprehensive information from the original design, construction, and operational phases. Once a pipeline is re-qualified for a new fluid, it can be re-commissioned under revised design specifications and operational parameters.

Recognizing that the repurposing of offshore pipelines for the transportation of hydrogen is a new concept for the industry, DNV has issued a detailed protocol to HyDelta, based on the latest DNV service specification DNV -SE-0657 [10]. The objective of DNV-SE-0657 is to provide a consistent approach and methodology for the re-qualification of pipelines systems to be used for the transportation of CO₂ and hydrogen. The re-qualification process proposed in this service specification involves a series of compliance checks, with the aim of documenting an overall level of safety and integrity equivalent to that required for a new pipeline. The protocol is designed to systematically and comprehensively address each individual step of DNV's outlined ten-step process, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – DNV’s ten-step process for the re-qualification of pipeline systems [10], [11]

The steps are as follows:

- Step1: Initiation,
- Step 2: Define basic operational parameters,
- Step 3: Safety assessment,
- Step 4: Current integrity,
- Step 5: Review of basis design,
- Step 6: Hydraulic assessment,
- Step 7: Safety and integrity reassessment,
- Step 8: Identify modifications,
- Step 9: Document,
- Step 10: Implement.

DNV’s ten-step process is intended to assess the current integrity of the pipeline, to evaluate the anticipated new operational parameters, and to identify potential new damage mechanisms and failure modes associated with hydrogen service for offshore pipelines.

The detail and effort required for each step depends on the available information and data, with assessment outputs potentially used for cost-benefit analyses. Access to comprehensive and valid documentation is crucial for a robust re-qualification process, and an integrity management system may support initial data gathering. This system typically includes original design records, as-built

construction and installation records, operational parameters, maintenance and inspection records, and documentation of repairs or modifications.

When repurposing pipelines for hydrogen service, all properties of hydrogen gas such as wider range of ignitable gas concentration in air, lower ignition energies (higher ignition probability) and potentially higher explosion pressure (detonation) need to be considered.

The extent and depth of required information typically increase as the re-qualification project progresses. Initially, a screening or concept study may be conducted using high-level information. The records needed encompass original design details, construction deviations, operational limits, and maintenance histories, ensuring a thorough understanding of the pipeline's condition and history. This comprehensive approach ensures the re-qualification process is well-informed and effective. While some re-qualifications can be completed by reviewing available information and documentation, additional activities are often necessary due to incomplete data, inadequate technical requirements for the new fluid, or unsuitable materials and equipment for the new transport conditions.

6.1 Step 1 – Initiation

Re-qualification of an existing pipeline for the transport of hydrogen shall commence with an evaluation of the technical and environmental risks. A risk assessment shall be performed, and a project risk register established during the initiation phase. This is used to identify all relevant risks associated with a different type of product. The risk register is considered a live document that shall be updated as required throughout the duration of the re-qualification project. During the initiation of a re-qualification process, several key aspects are to be considered, including:

- Battery Limits: Defining the scope of the pipeline's operational capacity.
- Design and Operational Parameters: Reviewing the pipeline's original design basis alongside established operational parameters to ensure compatibility with hydrogen transport.
- Critical Equipment and Components: Evaluating the key equipment and components within the battery limits, focusing on their material selection and pressure ratings.
- Design Modifications: Assessing any alterations to the design basis and operational parameters that may be necessitated by the new product.
- Operational History: Analysing the pipeline's historical performance and any precedents that could influence its re-qualification.
- Deviation from national standards and regulations.

The information collated during the initiation phase is instrumental in conducting an integrity assessment. This assessment, coupled with a gap analysis, is vital for identifying discrepancies between the original and the new design or construction standards. Such an analysis illuminates additional requirements or modifications needed to ensure the pipeline's readiness for hydrogen transport. It is important to establish the requirements that infrastructure should meet to be able to transport hydrogen.

6.2 Step 2 – Define basic operational parameters

Operational parameters for the re-qualified pipeline shall be established in this step. This includes aspects such as:

- Capacity, i.e. the amount of energy or fluid volume to be transported.
- Delivery pressure, this will be defined by the assets at the start and end of the pipeline.
- Composition of the new fluid, this will influence integrity and safety studies to follow.

6.3 Step 3 – Safety assessment

For pipelines and risers repurposed for hydrogen, Quantitative Risk Analysis (QRA) is essential for evaluating and managing associated risks. This process entails a systematic assessment that identifies, quantifies, and analyses potential hazards, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the risks involved.

Additionally, the following safety studies should all be reviewed to account for the differences in hydrogen and natural gas consequences.

- Installation HAZID and HAZOP – focus on the Nodes containing the riser ESDVs and pig launching.
- Installation dropped object study – with the emphasis of prevention of lifting over the live hydrogen pipelines and in the vicinity of the riser(s).
- Installation ship collision study – with the emphasis on preventing supply ships and or access vessels from approaching and impacting the hydrogen riser(s).
- Evacuation Escape and Rescue studies to ensure continued availability and survivability of life saving equipment such as life rafts and TEMPSCs post a hydrogen fire or explosion.
- Performance standards of riser ESDVs – review and rework of acceptable hydrogen leak rates and required valve closure times.
- Review and update of studies associated with defining levels of Passive Fire Protection on equipment and structures in vicinity of hydrogen risers, riser ESDV and pig launcher.
- Update of the installation ATEX and Hazardous Area Classification studies to account for presence of hydrogen.
- If the landfall receiving site (usually a gas terminal) falls under the Seveso III Directive (2012) site then the Site Safety Report will need to be updated to account for the hydrogen pipeline, isolation ESDV and pig receiver being in hydrogen service. The update should include reviewing the section on domino risks.

6.3.1 Pipeline and riser boundaries for the assessment

The boundaries are defined in section 1.2 of NEN3656-2022. Figure 3 and

Figure 3 – Locations on Offshore Installations Where Hydrogen Releases Can Occur With and Without Pig Launching Facilities

show the consequences of failures in the offshore and landfall sections of the pipeline. Figure 3 shows two cases, on the left the case with no pig launcher on the installation and on the right the case with a pig launcher

Figure 3 – Locations on Offshore Installations Where Hydrogen Releases Can Occur With and Without Pig Launching Facilities

Figure 4 – Locations at Landfall Sites Where Hydrogen Releases Can Occur

For the offshore section on the installation, hydrogen releases can occur from equipment failure between the upstream side of the riser ESDV or if there is a pig launcher the upstream side of the pigging isolation valve down to where the riser goes subsea at lowest astronomical tide (LAT). These releases are all above sea level. Subsea releases from the riser and pipeline can also occur. These are normally modelled to the installation 500m exclusion zone.

6.3.2 Potential consequences of hydrogen release

The potential consequences of releases above sea level are:

- The hydrogen release remains unignited and disperses naturally, e.g. a release directed away from the installation with a wind that directs the gas away from the topsides.
- The hydrogen release ignites immediately, and a stable jet fire is formed at the failure point.

- The hydrogen release is directed into the installation but does not ignite immediately and a cloud builds up until a delayed ignition source is encountered. The gas cloud ignites and there is either an explosion or a detonation depending on the level of topside congestion. A jet fire may subsequently form at the failure point.

Where there is a subsea riser or pipeline release, hydrogen is released into the sea water where its momentum is relatively quickly dissipated. The hydrogen bubbles rise to the surface where the gas enters the atmosphere with low velocity across a relatively large bubble zone. The size of the bubble zone through which the hydrogen enters the atmosphere is proportional to the depth of the release. The behaviour of the hydrogen cloud at the sea-air interface is highly dependent on the wind conditions at the sea surface and the buoyancy of the hydrogen.

Depending on the location of the subsea release the hydrogen may drift and rise towards the installation topsides or a support vessel if present and find an ignition source. Should the dispersing hydrogen cloud ignite there is likely to be an explosion/detonation which may burn back to form a stable sea surface fire.

For pipeline releases that occur at the landfall sites the following consequences are possible:

- The hydrogen release is subsea but sufficiently close to the land for it to be blown by wind to the land and ignition source. There could be an explosion/detonation at the land site which may burn back to a stable sea surface fire.
- The hydrogen release is in a buried section on route to the first landfall isolation or pig receiver isolation valve, then a crater can be formed at the release point. If ignited immediately then a hydrogen jet fire occurs, if ignition of the hydrogen cloud is delayed then an explosion/detonation is likely which may burn back to a stable jet fire at the release site in the crater.
- The hydrogen release is from the above ground section up to the first ESDV isolation or the pig receiver isolation and ignites immediately then a jet fire occurs, if the hydrogen cloud forms and drifts finding a delayed ignition source an explosion/detonation could occur this may burn back to a stable jet fire at the release site.

In Appendix 7 and 8, the various release rates and potential consequences of hydrogen release are described, and a comparison is made with the equivalent consequences of natural gas.

6.3.3 Quantitative Risk Analysis (QRA)

This process not only assesses the likelihood and impact of hazardous events but also involves the proposal and implementation of risk reduction measures. The result of a QRA is an estimation of the risk to surrounding people, property, and/or environment which can be used to help decision makers determine an acceptable level of risk [12]. Offshore pipelines carrying natural gas are subject of a quantitative risk assessment (QRA) described in the normative Annex D of the NEN 3656. The criteria for external safety is outlined in the chapter 6.7.2 of the NEN 3656. The landfall is considered as an area for the attention. The local risk (LR) for landfall $LR \leq 10^{-6}$. The group risk (GR) shall also be evaluated for the landfall. [13]

Pipeline and riser release frequencies

There are several failure mechanisms that could cause pipeline failure. The main mechanisms that cause failure of natural gas transmission pipelines in Europe are corrosion, external interference, mechanical defects, ground movement and others [14]. Most of these failure causes are independent of the pipeline transmission content. A key difference between natural gas and hydrogen relates to hydrogen embrittlement that may occur in cracks of the internal pipeline surfaces that could potentially increase the probability of mechanical failure, this accounts for less than 15% of the failures of natural gas transmission onshore pipelines in the period 1997 to 2016 [14].

Based on published references that are available (see Appendix 6) it is currently proposed that the same failure frequencies be adopted as for natural gas, for new hydrogen pipelines with no pressure cycling. Where a repurposed pipeline will be subjected to pressure cycling in hydrogen service, the application of a factor to increase failure frequencies following pipeline-specific review and analysis would be appropriate. For that reason PARLOC 2001 [15] pipeline and riser failure frequencies that are quoted in NEN 3656:2022 Table D.1 continue to be used for repurposed submarine pipelines, where in-service pressure cycling is not present; this data is reproduced below in

Table 3.

Table 3 – Recommended Failure Frequencies for Repurposed Submarine Pipelines and Risers¹

Pipeline Component	Category	Failure Frequency	Unit
Submarine pipeline in open sea	Submarine pipeline from well to installation (transport of untreated fluid)	5.0×10^{-4}	per km/year
	Treated oil or gas with pipeline diameter less than or equal to 24 inches	5.1×10^{-5}	per km/year
	Treated oil or gas with pipeline diameter greater than 24 inches	1.4×10^{-5}	per km/year
Submarine pipeline with external loads within the safety zone around platform	Treated oil or gas with pipeline diameter less than or equal to 16 inches	7.9×10^{-4}	per year
	Treated oil or gas with pipeline diameter greater than 16 inches	1.9×10^{-4}	per year
Flexible submarine pipelines	All diameters	2.3×10^{-3}	per km/year
Risers to platforms	Steel - diameter less than or equal to 16 inches	9.1×10^{-4}	per km/year
	Steel - diameter greater than 16 inches	1.2×10^{-4}	per km/year
	Flexible pipelines all diameters	6.0×10^{-3}	per km/year

Probability of Ignition

¹ Applicable for pipelines and risers which are not subject to in-service pressure cycling which may increase the mechanical failure cause by hydrogen embrittlement.

Guidance on ignition modelling published by the IOGP [16] recommends that “the values given in the look-up correlation are doubled” for hydrogen. The look-up correlations referred to use mass flow rate; hence, this recommendation is that for the same mass flow rate of hydrogen as methane the ignition probability should be doubled. The Dutch safety regulator, RIVM [16] gives ignition probabilities for different reactivity fuels, see Table 4, assuming hydrogen is categorised as “high reactivity”. For gaseous hydrogen, based on the current modeling by RIVM the probability of immediate ignition is 1. This means that hydrogen is assumed to always ignite immediately, and the calculation does not account for fire and explosion scenarios resulting from delayed ignition. However, RIVM is currently conducting research into the risks associated with hydrogen transport. This research indicates, based on case studies, that hydrogen does not always ignite immediately. For calculations concerning the risks of hydrogen transport, a different ignition probability will be used, estimated to be in the range of 0.8 to 1. The HyRAM technical guide [17] gives ignition probabilities for hydrogen and methane, see table below. The release rate categories are different for the different fuels, but comparing the maximum value for each fuel gives a factor of 1.2 for hydrogen, noting that this maximum value occurs at a lower mass flowrate for hydrogen than for methane.

Table 4 – Probability of direct ignition for stationary installations, RIVM

Continuous Releases	Instantaneous Releases	Probability of Immediate Ignition	
		Average/High Reactivity	Low Reactivity
<10 kg/s	<1000kg	0.2	0.02
10 to 100kg/s	1000 to 10,000kg	0.5	0.04
>100 kg/s	>10,000kg	0.7	0.09

Table 5 – Default ignition probabilities for different fuels, SANDIA

Hydrogen			Methane		
Release Rate (kg/s)	Ignition Probability		Release Rate (kg/s)	Ignition Probability	
	Immediate	Delayed		Immediate	Delayed
<0.125	0.008	0.004	<1	0.007	0.003
0.125 to 6.25	0.053	0.027	1 to 50	0.047	0.023
>6.25	0.230	0.120	>50	0.200	0.100

The recommended approach for modelling hydrogen ignition probabilities for leaks at the pipeline landfall site and on offshore installations is to apply a factor of 2 to the ignition probability derived from a natural gas mass flowrate-based model (subject to a maximum ignition probability of 1). However, there is significant uncertainty due to the limited evidence available compared with natural gas and differing values that are given in the published literature.

Ignition Timing

Experimental releases from ruptures of large bore high pressure hydrogen pipelines have been undertaken by DNV at its Spadeadam test site in the UK. The releases were designed so that immediate ignition did not occur, however self-ignition of the gas released occurred after a very short delay (~100ms) under uncontrolled but idealised rupture conditions (without soil) and the result confirmed that significant overpressures can be generated by ignition of hydrogen pipeline rupture releases. When modelling the ignition timing for releases at landfall sites and the installation the following recommendations are made:

- Ignition probability for hydrogen pipeline ruptures is 1.0 (i.e. all hydrogen pipeline/riser rupture releases are expected to ignite when they encroach on a landfall site or installation).
- The split between immediate and delayed ignition should be in the ratio 2/3:1/3 [18] which means that the proportion of immediately ignited releases is assumed to be higher for hydrogen than for natural gas. This is in line with the observations made above regarding the wider flammability range and lower minimum ignition energy of hydrogen.
- For thermal radiation calculations, it is assumed that all ignitions are immediate. It is likely that delayed ignition of a hydrogen release will occur earlier than delayed ignition of the equivalent natural gas release.
- For overpressure calculations, it is assumed that both immediate and delayed ignition events have the potential to generate appreciable overpressures and therefore it is recommended that calculations be undertaken for two cases as follows:
 - For immediate ignition (2/3 of the time), the overpressure is calculated for the total mass of released gas at 100 ms.
 - For delayed ignition (1/3 of the time), the overpressure is calculated for the time at which the hydrogen plume has fully established and is at its largest (this is calculated on a case-by-case basis and is typically between 5-15 seconds).

Hydrogen explosion and detonation

Estimation of hydrogen explosion risk is essential. A hydrogen explosion could be a serious consequence from a hydrogen leak (and ignition) in an enclosed or semi-open space such as a cellar deck on an installation, and this scenario might for certain conditions lead to high explosion overpressures (including detonation overpressures). Therefore, extensive risk analyses may be necessary to fully understand and mitigate the risks associated with hydrogen explosions.

For hydrogen, it is further possible to obtain Deflagration to Detonation Transition (DDT) with a relatively small cloud or within a small, confined area, whereas methane/natural gas does not detonate in real conditions. The characteristics of a detonation can cause the risk to increase even more in an open area if the flammable cloud extends outside a congested region. This is because when a detonation has started in a congested region, it can also sustain itself outside that region even if not congested. If a large hydrogen cloud fills first a congested region, and then continues outside this region, a DDT can happen in the gas within the congested region, reaching up to 10–20 barg. Such a detonation can continue in the unburnt gas outside the congested space with an ongoing detonation until the end of the cloud is reached. Designing or protecting structures and equipment from the overpressure levels cause by detonation is not practical. Therefore, mitigation methods such a reducing leaks sources, ignition sources and congestion should be focussed on.

Congestion may be encountered:

- On the topsides of an installation
- At landfall if there are buildings or trees
- At the site of the pig receiver or landfall ESDV

When modelling hydrogen explosions at the landfall site or the installation:

- The worst case should include the possibility of detonation.
- The flammable inventory should be defined by the fuel mass within the 10% to 75% contours
- Use the TNO Multi Energy Model 10 curve (15 Bar source).

Subsea releases 1500m from either the installation or the landfall site are unlikely to ignite or find any congestion so are likely to disperse naturally without ignition.

6.4 Step 4 – Data gathering and integrity assessment

To assess the readiness of an existing natural gas network for conversion to hydrogen service, the compatibility/suitability of the entire system should be evaluated. An initial screening or concept study should be conducted with high-level and approximate information. This includes:

- Analysing and understanding the material properties of the pipelines
- Evaluating the current state of the infrastructure, including any existing flaws.
- Assessing the design and construction standards originally used and their relevance to hydrogen service.
- Identifying and prioritizing sections of the network that may require upgrades or modifications.
- Estimating the cost and feasibility of necessary changes to accommodate hydrogen.
- Reviewing regulatory and safety requirements specific to hydrogen transport.

Prior to the implementation and transition to a new operational mode the most complete and accurate data must be obtained.

6.4.1 Required data for the assessment

Historical data and the available information from an integrity management process/program may be a beneficial source, however this may not necessarily provide all information needed (e.g. lack of inspections documenting current status, lack of operation data, lack of design documents). Identification of materials as well as the pressure rating and the current condition of the pipeline system are key information that shall be screened as part of the integrity assessment. Inspections information will be required to identify the current level of corrosion (wall thickness reduction), any existing defects, and sizes of any weld cracks. Construction and installation records will also need to be examined, including concessions and deviations from the design documents.

The initial data gathering process for the pipeline and should normally include:

- Determination of the original design code, pipe specification and standards used for fittings and equipment (e.g. valves)
- Original design records, including but not limited to the identification and selection of materials and the pressure rating
- Welding procedure specification (WPS) and Welder Performance Qualifications (WPQ)
- As-built construction records, including concessions and deviations from the design documents
- Original operational parameters and limitations of the pipeline
- Operational records, including maintenance, inspection, pressure cycling, free spans, and testing records spanning the life of the pipeline
- Records associated with any repairs/modifications (e.g. hot taps) or any other intervention necessary, including equipment or components within the battery limits.

Offshore pipelines, being in operation, are usually subjects of life extension efforts. Over time, they are subjected to harsh marine environments, leading to corrosion and other forms of degradation. Therefore, regular assessments and life extension efforts are essential to ensure their continued safe and efficient operation. A life extension report for offshore pipelines typically includes a comprehensive evaluation of the pipeline's current condition, which is crucial for planning future operations and potential conversions.

In addition to assessing the physical state of the pipeline, the repurposing study should conduct a risk assessment to identify and mitigate potential risks associated with continued operation or conversion. Maintenance and repair recommendations are provided to address any identified issues, offering guidelines on necessary repairs, reinforcements, and best practices for ongoing maintenance to extend the pipeline's life. Furthermore, life extension efforts for offshore pipelines are vital to maintain their structural integrity, ensure safety, and optimize their operational life span. Integrating the findings from a life extension report with detailed engineering assessments and project-specific considerations is crucial for ensuring that the pipeline continues to operate safely and efficiently and can be converted for hydrogen.

Missing data

In cases where material property data for older pipelines is limited due to missing records or changes in ownership, efforts must be made to obtain this data through available means. This may involve retrieving copies of original records, consulting secondary sources, examining similar components with known properties, or verifying quality control procedures from the time of installation. Several potential sources of information should be considered:

- a) Copies of Primary Records: Photocopies or scanned versions of the original records that detail the properties and specifications of the pipeline components.
- b) Other Original Records: Any available documents from the time of construction that provide information on the material properties of the pipeline components.
- c) Secondary Records: Records that may not be primary but still offer valuable insights into the pipeline's material properties, such as maintenance logs, inspection reports, or third-party evaluations.
- d) Evidence of Similar Components: Documentation or records of similar components from the same manufacturer, installed around the same time, which have completed and accurate primary records.
- e) Quality Control Procedures: Documentation that demonstrates the quality control measures in place during the time of installation, which can provide confidence in the material properties even if direct records are lacking.

If necessary, operators should also consider removing samples for testing to ensure comprehensive material characterization. Some of the tests are outlined in Appendix 2.

Please note that, ASME B31.12 requires a sampling rate of one examination per 1.6 km (1 mile) of pipeline. However, the rationale behind this distance-based sampling approach is not entirely clear, particularly when considering pipelines composed of varying pipe sizes, grades, vintages, or manufacturers. A uniform sampling rate may not adequately capture the material variability across the entire pipeline.

To address this concern, the application of statistical methods can provide a more robust assurance of material characterization. By employing techniques similar to those used in structural reliability analysis for pipeline uprating studies, it is possible to design a practical sampling scheme that better accounts for the pipeline's specific characteristics. Such methods would allow for a more accurate assessment of material properties, ensuring that the sampling strategy reflects the true variability and

risks associated with the pipeline. This approach would enhance confidence in the pipeline's integrity, even in the absence of complete historical data.

6.4.2 Integrity assessment

Where an operator is considering conversion of an existing pipeline to hydrogen service, suitability of pipeline materials must be thoroughly assessed in order to ensure that hydrogen embrittlement (HE) does not negatively impact the pipelines' integrity. Furthermore, the pipeline must meet the essential safety requirements of NEN 3650-1 and NEN 3656. In addition, requirements for crossing water barriers (landfalls) may apply from NEN 3651.

Hydrogen Embrittlement (HE) manifests itself by a degradation of steel ductility properties, the initiation of internal cracks (with or without applied stresses), delayed failure ruptures, reduced fatigue lives or reduced stress intensity factors for the initiation of cracks [19].

HE indicates a type of damage where atomic hydrogen permeates into high-stress regions, like crack-like flaws, in pipe steel. This results in reduced ductility and fracture toughness. Often recognized as a risk for materials vulnerable to hydrogen, HE can influence the performance and structural soundness by:

- Decreasing fracture toughness
- Decreased fatigue cracking resistance
- Increased FCGR
- Decreased ductility

Fracture toughness is an indicator of a material's resistance to crack propagation under stress. When fracture toughness is reduced, the magnitude of a crack leading to failure is also diminished. Additionally, an increased fatigue crack growth rate (FCGR) signifies that a defect will attain a critical dimension more quickly with fewer stress repetitions, consequently reducing the operational lifespan of an element subjected to hydrogen embrittlement (HE).

Multiple factors influence the severity of hydrogen embrittlement and the resulting deterioration of mechanical properties. These include the operating temperature and pressure, the partial pressure of hydrogen at the pipe surface, metallurgical characteristics like microstructure type and grain size, the direction of stress in relation to the plate rolling direction, and the existence of anomalies such as cracks, laminations, inclusions, and flaws in welding.

Material compatibility

One of the primary issues with using current natural gas infrastructure for hydrogen is how hydrogen could negatively affect the mechanical and metallurgical characteristics of steels. The ASME B31.12 offers general guidelines on materials that are suitable for use with hydrogen. Yet, the materials are only categorized as 'acceptable' or 'not acceptable,' with little explanation or detail on the reasons, or the conditions that might render them suitable. ASME B31.12 generally recommends the use of lower steel grades for pipelines but allows higher-strength steel grades under specific conditions, provided their performance is thoroughly validated. For offshore pipelines, which are subjected to higher pressures, even lower-grade materials must be derated using a material performance factor when operating at pressures exceeding 138 bar.

For the pipeline material evaluation, ASME B31.12 offers two options for determining design pressure: a prescriptive option (A) and a performance-based option (B). Each option has different material requirements, see Appendix 1.

For a comprehensive compatibility assessment, it's necessary to classify pipeline materials and components by considering their material specifications, properties, design, and operational factors. To begin, pipelines can be grouped according to their operating pressure and the grade of material used for an overview analysis. Key factors that affect the integrity of pipelines in hydrogen services encompass the maximum allowable operating pressure as a percentage of specified minimum yield strength (MAOP as % SMYS), material hardness, any pre-existing flaws, type of seam, and any prior instances of failure.

Current Integrity

DNV-RP-F116 [20] in Chapter 6.1.6 establishes how the integrity assessment process should be performed based on historical data for offshore pipelines. The data obtained from the integrity assessment shall be properly documented to ensure traceability and enable trending.

Figure 5 – Example of integrity assessment process according to DNV-RP-F116 [20]

The integrity study should establish that the integrity of the existing offshore natural gas pipeline has not been adversely affected during the operation, meaning that the original design pressure has not been reduced and the pipeline is fit for service. If the integrity study shows that integrity has been adversely affected and the design pressure has been lowered, this may be acceptable provided the intended working pressure is lower or the cause of the lowered design pressure has been remediated. An internal pipeline inspection to determine the current wall thickness is mandatory if there is no other evidence available to determine that the wall thickness has not been affected by corrosion or damage.

For corrosion related threats, in-line inspection provides the best basis for a condition assessment as it enables full inspection coverage, and good detection and sizing capabilities [20]. For this reason, this protocol requires that all pipelines be piggable or, at least, capable of becoming piggable, due to the necessity of detecting existing defects and understanding how these defects can affect the remaining integrity of the pipeline for hydrogen service.

As part of the integrity evaluation before repurposing to hydrogen, the operator needs to understand the impact of potential contamination that can be found in existing offshore natural gas networks on hydrogen purity and to define an approach for cleaning such pipelines. Typically, there can be a range of different contaminations in upstream offshore natural gas pipelines including sulfur and H₂S, organo-halogens, solids and waxes, mercury and others. Each of these contaminants poses different challenges and risks for the pipeline integrity and safety, see Appendix 3. Therefore, the pipeline cleaning process used to assess and clean an existing offshore natural gas pipeline must ensure it is ready for hydrogen transport. This process, detailed in Appendix 4, is based on industry best practices for pigging pipelines and incorporates direct experience from small diameter onshore natural gas pipelines.

Pipeline integrity during hydrogen service

The most significant types of defects in the case of hydrogen service are those that reduce the fatigue life of the pipeline such as crack like flaws. However, other types of defects that also reduce the fatigue life such as dents could also prove to be challenging for hydrogen service. Fatigue lives in hydrogen can be 50 to 100 times shorter than in natural gas although this is strongly dependent on the magnitude, the number and the rate (duration) of cycles. The larger the cyclic stresses, the greater the reduction in fatigue life for hydrogen service. It is usually assumed that repurposed hydrogen pipelines will likely be operated under similar conditions to natural gas in terms of pressure fluctuations. In practice, this may not be the case. When considering the potential conversion of natural gas pipelines for hydrogen, operators need to evaluate the likelihood that expected pressure cycles will produce acceptable (very low) fatigue crack growth.

After decades of operation with natural gas, it is expected that corrosion defects may also exist. These defects may be activated by the presence of hydrogen. It is recommended to perform a pipeline inspection to determine if anomalies are present and to size them. Besides it is recommended to determine the critical defect size and to monitor crack-like defects during the hydrogen service.

The existing inspection intervals for natural gas shall be assessed and evaluated as to whether they are sufficient for hydrogen based on the anticipated FCGR. It should be noted that detailed guidance for the assessment of different types of anomalies that could be present on an offshore pipeline is discussed in more detail in Section 6.4.3.

Inline inspection

Hydrogen service may potentially result in accelerated crack growth rates and reduced critical flaw sizes, which may require higher resolution ILI tools capable of detecting and sizing smaller flaws, having dimensions smaller than (or at least a reliable minimum detection size not larger than) the size of a crack that could grow to failure before the next inspection. Pipelines intended for re-qualification to hydrogen service must be designed or modified to allow for the passage of ILI tools. This ensures regular and thorough inspections can be conducted, enabling the detection of any flaws that may compromise the integrity of the pipeline under hydrogen service conditions.

When re-qualifying an existing pipeline for the transport of hydrogen, several advanced inspection and measurement techniques can be employed to evaluate the pipeline's integrity and identify potential issues. The following techniques may be applied:

- Electromagnetic Acoustic Transducer (EMAT): Generates ultrasonic waves using electromagnetic fields. EMAT is useful for inspecting the pipeline's wall thickness and detecting cracks. Limited to longitudinal weld defect detection
- Magnetic Flux Leakage (MFL): This technique detects corrosion, pitting, and other defects in the pipeline. It involves magnetizing the pipeline and then detecting changes in the magnetic field caused by anomalies.
- Acoustic Resonance Technology (ART): Uses resonant frequencies to detect changes in material properties and identify defects in gas-filled pipelines.
- Eddy Current Testing (ECT): Employs electromagnetic induction to detect surface and near-surface defects in conductive materials.
- Ultrasonic Crack Detection (UTCD): Uses high-frequency sound waves to detect and size cracks within the pipeline material. The technique involves sending ultrasonic waves into the pipeline and analysing the reflected signals to identify cracks. Limited to detection in liquids, girth weld.
- Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU): Uses sensors to monitor the tools accelerations and angular rate to identify locations of curvature and bending strain.

The POF White paper "In-line inspection tool readiness for hydrogen pipelines" published in May 2024 [21] and NEN 3656 section 11.5 "Internal pipe inspection by intelligent pigs" provides further explanation of the capabilities of ILI.

It should be recognised that based on the current status and capabilities of inline inspection techniques it will be very challenging to reliably detect and size crack like flaws located in the pipeline welds, particularly in girth welds. When using ILI tools to determine the current integrity status of the pipeline it is of critical importance to review the tool specifications and identify the types and sizes of anomalies that can and can't be reliably detected. The aim of this review is to identify what types and sizes of anomalies could be present on the pipeline that were not detected by the ILI. These undetected defects will also need to be considered in any repurposing assessment unless there is any alternative evidence available to discount the risk of such a defect being present.

6.4.3 Defect assessment

Any anomalies reported as part of an inline inspection (ILI) will require an assessment to confirm that are fit for service. For those anomalies subject to a degradation mechanism a remaining life assessment also be required to determine a suitable time to reinspection or repair. For natural gas pipelines fitness

for service assessments are undertaken in accordance with established codes such as API 579-1, BS 7910, ASME B31G, and DNV-RP-F101. However, given that pipeline materials can degrade due to the presence of hydrogen embrittlement it is essential to consider the potential affect this may have on the criteria for acceptable flaw sizes.

Primarily the presence of hydrogen in a pipeline will result in a reduction in the material fracture toughness and an increase in the fatigue crack growth rate. Therefore, it can be considered that hydrogen will primarily impact those anomalies that reduce the fatigue life of a pipeline and those whose failure is governed by the material fracture toughness. The general types of anomalies reported on the pipeline are listed below (as per anomalies listed in API 579). The potential impact of hydrogen on the assessment of these types of anomalies are discussed in the following sections.

- Corrosion (External and Internal)
- Milling / Manufacturing Anomaly
- Dent
- Gouge
- Ovality
- Crack
- Lamination
- Bending strain / pipeline curvature
- Free spans

Any guidance for the assessment of defects in a hydrogen pipeline should be treated as additional requirements to those already needed for a natural gas pipeline. Any anomaly or defect that is considered unacceptable for operation in a natural gas will also be unacceptable for operation in a hydrogen pipeline. It should be recognised that prior to re-purposing any existing anomalies on the pipeline that may have been previously assessed as acceptable will need to re-evaluate for hydrogen operation.

Corrosion

It is stated in ASME B31.12 that corrosion (external or internal) can be assessed in accordance with ASME B31G, Manual for Determining the Remaining Strength of Corroded Pipelines, or other accepted method. However, it should be noted that, similar to the other anomalies, this is predicated on the assumption that the pipe material shows sufficient toughness following the materials testing. If the pipe material exceeds the minimum toughness criteria provided in standards such as API 5L then it can be assumed that any corrosion anomaly would fail in a ductile manner and hence the standard assessment methods such as ASME B31G will be applicable. However, if the pipe material is found to exhibit a low toughness, then it is possible that any corrosion anomalies could fail in a brittle manner, i.e. fracture rather than plastic collapse. In this case the standard assessment codes would not be applicable as they will provide non-conservative failure predictions.

DNV-RP-F101 states that the assessment procedure is not recommended for applications where fracture is likely to occur. This may include materials with Charpy values of less than 27 J full size test (equivalent 2/3 scale is 18 J) and for the weld a minimum full size Charpy value of 30 J is recommended. A corresponding required toughness could be calculated for a pipeline using the guidance provided in

Annex J of BS 7910. If the expected fracture toughness of a pipeline under hydrogen operation is below these limits, then it will be necessary to model a corrosion anomaly as a crack to ensure a conservative assessment.

It should also be noted that the standard corrosion assessment codes assume that any anomalies are blunt. Short, sharp pitting anomalies could potentially behave more like a crack and be at risk of failure by fracture rather than plastic collapse. In pipelines sharp pitting anomalies are more likely to be associated with internal corrosion. Categorisation of any pit would need to consider the depth profile of the anomaly to confirm if it is flat bottomed or has a sharp base. Sharp corrosion anomalies will need to be assessed as cracks for fracture and fatigue failure modes.

Milling / Manufacturing Anomaly

Pipeline milling anomalies are generally considered to be acceptable given that will have been introduced during construction and as such will have experienced the hydrotest during commissioning. However, as hydrogen reduces the fracture toughness of material, reliance on hydrotest survival (when the hydrogen was not present) is a less convincing argument going forward, particularly if any flaws are sharp crack like defects. Milling anomalies are usually relatively shallow and are likely to be acceptable following conversion to hydrogen, provided that materials testing can show that retains a moderate level of toughness.

The largest potential defects in seam or girth welds are likely to be larger than most milling anomalies and more severe in terms of susceptibility to fracture. Qualification of the pipe material and welds for hydrogen operation will be sufficient to provide assurance that any pre-existing mill and manufacturing anomalies will also be acceptable.

Dents

The presence of a dent will result a variation in the hoop stress around the circumference of the pipe and local stress concentrations. In general, plain dents do not significantly reduce the static strength of the pipe. However, the stress concentrations caused by the presence of the dent will increase the magnitude of stresses at the location and as such reduce the fatigue life. The fatigue life of a pipe containing a dent will be lower than the fatigue life of a plain circular pipe.

Guidance for the assessment of dents in a hydrogen pipeline is provided in ASME B31.12 where it is stated that plain dents are injurious if they exceed a depth of 6% of the nominal pipe diameter. In addition, plain dents of any depth are acceptable, provided strain levels associated with the deformation do not exceed 2% strain. When compared to the guidance in ASME B31.8 for a natural gas pipeline there is no change in depth limit of 6% however, the strain limit for a dent is 6% rather than 2% for a hydrogen pipeline.

Dents that affect ductile girth or seam welds are injurious if they exceed a depth of 2% of the nominal pipe diameter, except those evaluated and determined to be safe by an engineering analysis provided strain levels associated with the deformation do not exceed 2%. It is further noted that dents of any depth that affect nonductile welds, such as acetylene girth welds or seam welds that are prone to brittle fracture, are injurious. Therefore, it will be necessary to prove that the pipeline seam and girth welds are considered to be ductile when exposed to hydrogen through testing before any dents affecting welds can be considered to be acceptable. When compared to the guidance in ASME B31.8

for a natural gas pipeline there is no change in depth limit of 6% however, the strain limit for a dent on a weld is 4% rather than 2% for a hydrogen pipeline.

It should be noted that the acceptable strain limit for a dent in a hydrogen pipeline is lower than that for natural gas pipeline. Therefore, it may be necessary to reassess dents that have previously been considered to be fit for service for natural gas operation if the assessment was based on the predicted strain.

The main gap associated with dents in a hydrogen pipeline is the current absence of any guidance relating to the expected fatigue life. Given that exposure to hydrogen leads to an increase in the fatigue crack growth rate in steel it is possible that the fatigue life of a dent in a hydrogen pipeline could be significantly shorter than the fatigue life of a dent in a natural gas pipeline.

Currently the guidance in ASME B31.12 is the only definitive guidance for assessing dents in a hydrogen pipeline. Existing methods for the assessment of dents will need to be validated for hydrogen service to ensure that they remain conservative. This is likely to be addressed by industry wide research with the existing assessment approaches updated if required.

Gouge

A gouge is typically the result of surface damage to a pipeline that has displaced or removed material from the pipe wall, resulting in a metal loss type defect. Gouges can be introduced during construction however they are generally associated with third party damage. There is no guidance for the assessment of a gouge in ASME B31.12, they are treated as injurious regardless of size and would require a permanent repair.

The material at the base of a gouge will have been cold worked as part of the gouging process and this work hardened layer will have reduced ductility and can contain cracking. As such a gouge can act as an initiator for fatigue crack. In general, a gouge will have a lower static strength and fatigue life than an undamaged section of pipe.

The failure pressure of a gouge can be calculated using the flow stress dependent NG-18 equations developed by Battelle in the 1960s and 1970s. This equation is only applicable if the upper shelf two-thirds size Charpy V-notch impact energy of the line pipe is greater than or equal to 21 J. However, it should be noted that if this approach is adopted it is typically combined with a dressing repair to remove at least 0.5 mm of material at the base of the gouge. The dressing is required to remove the risk of micro cracking at the base of the gouge that could potentially reduce the fatigue life of the defect. Given the increase in fatigue crack growth under hydrogen a dressing repair of gouge would be required unless it could be shown that the predicted fatigue life was acceptable.

A gouge could be conservatively modelled as a crack and assessed as such for hydrogen operation, accounting for the reduction toughness and increase in fatigue crack growth rate. If this assessment was carried out 0.5 mm should be added to the measured depth of the gouge to account for any micro cracking that could be present within the base of the feature.

Ovality

The presence of an ovality in a pipeline will result a variation in the hoop stress around the circumference of the pipe and local stress concentrations. These stress concentrations can result in a

reduction of the fatigue life. Any fatigue assessment for an ovality will need to include a factor of safety to account for the reduction in fatigue life due to the presence of hydrogen.

The static strength of a pipeline will only be affected by an ovality if the pipe material is of low toughness. The assessment procedures for an ovality assume that the pipeline will meet a minimum toughness requirement. Provided that the test programme can show that material toughness under hydrogen is above that required by the pipe standard, i.e. API 5L then the static strength should not be an issue and any ovality can be assessed using standard methods.

Similar to dents there is currently no definitive guidance available for predicting the fatigue life of an ovality. This will need to be addressed by industry wide research with the existing assessment approaches updated if required.

Cracks and Crack-Like Flaws

Cracks are planar flaws that are characterised by their length and depth with a sharp root radius. They can be surface breaking, embedded or in extreme cases through wall and are typically located in pipe welds. Types of anomalies that are normally treated as cracks from an integrity perspective include planar cracks, lack of fusion and lack of penetration in a weld, and sharp groove like corrosion features. It is sometimes advisable to treat some types of volumetric flaws as cracks if there is a risk that they could contain micro cracking at the root. As discussed in Section 0 this assumption can be used for gouges if it is not possible to remove the work hardened layer.

Cracks can be difficult to detect during normal inspection as their relatively small volume and likely location in a weld makes them difficult to identify using inline inspection techniques. If a crack is reported on a pipeline, it is important to understand the cause of the crack. Typically, cracks will have been present since commissioning and were introduced during line pipe manufacture, during transportation or during pipeline construction. It is also possible that a crack could have initiated at a weld during operation and grown in service due to fatigue until it reached a detectable size. However, cracks can also be indicative of larger integrity threats such as poor material properties, excessive loads, or the presence of conditions for environmental cracking.

For hydrogen operation, there are two main points to consider when assessing cracks or crack-like flaws; the material fracture toughness will decrease, and the fatigue crack growth rate will increase. As such cracks that were previously acceptable under natural gas operation may now be unacceptable under hydrogen operation. It should be noted that this concern forms the basis of the Option B assessment in ASME B31.12 for existing cracks that may not have been detected prior to repurposing. This is discussed in more detail in section 6.5.1.

For any cracks or crack-like flaws identified post re-purposing these can be assessed using standard fracture mechanics procedures such as those provided in BS 7910 or API 579-1 / ASME FFS-1. Any integrity assessment for a crack will consist of two parts; a fracture assessment based on the static stresses and a fatigue assessment based on the cyclic stresses. The key requirement for these calculations will be to use a hydrogen specific fracture toughness for the pipe in the fracture assessment and a hydrogen crack growth rate curve (such as that provided in ASME B31.12) in the fatigue assessment. Assumptions regarding other inputs in the calculations, such as welding residual stress and misalignment, should be taken from the assessment code if no measured data is available.

Lamination

Laminations represent internal separation of the pipe material which create layers in the pipe wall. They are formed during the manufacturing process and as such will have been present in the pipe since construction. They are typically parallel to the pipe surface and as such do not reduce the effective wall thickness.

For natural gas pipelines laminations can be assessed using Part 13 in API 579-1 / ASME FFS-1. However, for hydrogen operation API 579-1 / ASME FFS-1 requires the use of Part 7 for laminations. Part 7 in API 579-1 / ASME FFS-1 characterises laminations as either a blister or hydrogen induced cracking depending on their nature. It should be noted that Part 7 can only be used to assess a lamination if the pipeline was designed to a standard that meets the requirements of API 579-1 / ASME FFS-1 and that pipeline does not experience significant fatigue cycles. A pipeline that is not considered to be at risk of fatigue (as per API 579-1 / ASME FFS-1) is one that experiences less than 150 cycles (i.e., pressure and/or temperature variations including operational changes and start-ups and shut-downs) throughout its history and future planned operation or satisfies the cyclic service screening procedure in Part 14 (of API 579-1 / ASME FFS-1).

If a lamination can't be assessed using the procedures in Part 7 of API 579-1 / ASME FFS-1 then it can be modelled as a crack and assessed as such for hydrogen operation, accounting for the reduction in toughness and increase in fatigue crack growth rate.

Bending Strain / Curvature

Locations along a pipeline that have moved since construction can be subject to bending strain. These areas will typically be identified through a remotely operated vehicle (ROV) inspection or an inline inspection. There is no guidance in ASME B31.12 or any other relevant standards in terms of allowing a strain-based design for a pipeline containing hydrogen. Any assessments that have been carried out to confirm the acceptability of the pipeline for hydrogen operation (i.e. Option A or Option B in ASME B31.12) will not be applicable for an area of bending strain.

The assessment of an area subject to a strain-based design would require the development of a fracture resistance curve during material testing (i.e. a J-R curve) instead of a simple linear elastic fracture mechanics toughness parameter such as K_{IH} . There is however very little guidance on how such testing or analysis should be carried out, for example the maximum allowed amount of tearing associated with the strain limits described above.

It is recognised that this is a gap in the published standards currently available for pipelines transporting hydrogen. It is possible that this gap could be addressed in future updates to current standards, new standards or guidance documents. Potentially this could include new offshore standards where the use of strain-based fracture mechanics is more common than is the case for onshore pipelines.

Free Spans

A free span represents a section of the pipeline where the outer surface of the pipe is no longer in contact with the seabed. The main risks associated with free spans are buckling and vortex induced vibration which can result in a significantly shortened fatigue life. There are two main types of free spans that can occur on offshore pipelines:

- Scour-induced free spans caused by seabed erosion or bed-form activities. The free span scenarios (span length, gap ratio, etc.) may change with time.
- Unevenness-induced free spans caused by an irregular seabed profile. Normally the free span scenario is time invariant unless operational parameters such as pressure and temperature change significantly.

Free spans will be detected by a remotely operated vehicle (ROV) inspection rather than an ILI and can be assessed using DNV-RP-F105.

An initial screening assessment is undertaken as part of DNV-RP-F105 to determine if vortex induced vibration and as such fatigue is a risk at the free span. This assessment should not be affected for hydrogen operation, however, should the screening assessment fail, and a fatigue assessment is required then this could be impacted given the increased fatigue crack growth rate. It would be expected that free spans not currently at risk of vortex induced vibration will also not be at risk when exposed to hydrogen. However, any free spans failing this initial screening check could have reduced fatigue under hydrogen operation.

There is currently no specific guidance for the assessment of free spans in a hydrogen pipeline. It is possible that this gap could be addressed in future updates to offshore standards.

6.5 Step 5 – Review of design basis

Conducting a thorough review of the basis of design based on the results of the conclusions from the safety risk assessment, and the current integrity assessment ensures that all identified issues are considered and addressed. It helps in determining the necessary modifications to the pipeline, validating material compatibility, ensuring safe operational practices, and updating risk management strategies. This comprehensive evaluation is essential to safely and efficiently repurpose the pipeline for hydrogen transport, minimizing risks to infrastructure, personnel, and the environment. System requirements including maximum pressure and receiving pressure, shall be identified and included as part of a revised basis of design for the re-qualification.

Adding hydrogen will change in the operational conditions as:

- Maximum allowable pressure (MAOP) will be based on the current pipeline condition.
- Changes in gas composition, hydrogen has potential to hydrogen embrittlement.
- Gas velocity (related to transport capacity), due to low energy content, hydrogen velocity shall be increased.
- Design factor.
- Increase/decrease in pressure cycling (fatigue). Hydrogen can accelerate the crack growth.

Consider cyclic loads when determining operation scenarios: Hydrogen environments pose a higher risk of cyclic loads than natural gas or oil environments because they can speed up the rate of crack growth.

The MAOP can be determined with two options:

Option A: With this option it is possible to determine the maximum allowable operating pressure:

$$P = \frac{2t.S.F.E.T.Hf}{D}$$

- D = Pipe nominal outside diameter
- t = Nominal pipe wall thickness

- S = Specified minimum yield stress
- F = design factor. Location classes 1-3: 0.5; Location class 4: 0.4
- E = Joint factor (=1)
- T = Temperature de-rating factor (=1)
- Hf = Material performance factors

The formula takes in account material, dimensions and location (F) of the pipeline and the adverse effects of hydrogen gas on mechanical properties of carbon steel (Hf).

Option B: With this option it is possible to evaluate the pipeline design parameters using fracture mechanics by evaluating the fatigue crack growth of an existing defect for a given pipeline. The materials performance for this option factor Hf is set to 1 for all cases. The design factors for location class 1 increase from 0.5 (applicable to Option A) to 0.72 and the design factor for location class 2 to increase from 0.5 (applicable to Option A) to 0.6. ASME B31.12, option B provides an equation to calculate the fatigue crack growth rate.

$$\frac{da}{dN} = a1. \Delta K. b1 + \frac{1}{\frac{1}{a2. \Delta K^{b2}} + \frac{1}{a3. \Delta K^{b3}}}$$

- ΔK = Kmax – Kmin range stress intensify factor, see Appendix 2
- Kmin = minimum applied stress intensify factor
- Kmax = maximum applied stress intensify factor

Parameters a and b are from table PL 3.7.1-5, ASME B31.12-2023. Option B also requires threshold stress intensity factor measurements to be made for base, weld, and heat-affected zone materials to demonstrate resistance to hydrogen embrittlement. Option A reduces the operating pressure up to 50% compared to natural gas. Option B uses fracture mechanics and allows to achieve higher pressures like for natural gas.

Please note that ASME plans to revise the content of B31.12 and incorporate into ASME B31.8. A consensus engineering document has been published by PRCI explaining the proposed changes [22].

6.5.1 Undertaking an Option B Assessment

Carrying out an Option A assessment is relatively straightforward with only minimal information required to complete the calculations. However, there are more uncertainties associated with the Option B calculations and currently there is no detailed guidance available as to how these calculations should be carried out.

The main two assumptions regarding the Option B calculations are the appropriate fracture toughness for the pipe and the starting size of a welding flaw to use in the fracture calculation required to show that the pipe fracture toughness in hydrogen is acceptable at the required design pressure.

For the fracture toughness input the current guidance would require testing of the pipe material in a hydrogen environment to obtain a suitable value. It is possible in the future that a sufficient global database of results will be available to allow for recommended minimum values depending on pipe vintage and grade. However, at the present time testing of project specific pipe is the recommended approach to obtain a fracture toughness value to use in the calculations.

ASME B31.12 suggests the use of a welding flaw with a depth of 0.25 times the wall thickness and a length of 1.5 times the wall thickness. However, it is unclear how this relates to typical welding flaws

found in offshore pipelines. It is recommended instead to base the flaw size on welding specifications or inspection records if available. The length and depth of the flaw can be based on the probability of detection capabilities of the weld inspection technique used at construction, or the maximum allowable size used in the design engineering critical assessment. The aim of this review should be to provide a prediction of the maximum size of a flaw that could have been present in the weld at the time of construction. It is likely that is a conservative prediction and could potentially be improved by targeted inspection if an option.

It is important to recognise that for re-purposing pipelines it will be necessary to account for any potential fatigue growth since commissioning to the date of repurposing when identifying a flaw size to use in the calculations. As such a fatigue assessment will be required for the postulated flaw at construction to determine a suitable flaw size at repurposing. This fatigue assessment will need to consider all sources of stress cycling since construction.

ASME 31.12 is primarily intended for onshore pipelines and as such does not explicitly mention requiring an assessment for pipeline girth welds, the Option A and Option B calculations only consider seam welds. For an offshore pipeline there will be a requirement to consider undertaking similar calculations for girth welds given the potential for higher longitudinal stresses than would be expected in an onshore pipeline.

6.6 Step 6 – Hydraulic assessment

When repurposing a natural gas pipeline for hydrogen service, a hydraulic assessment is crucial due to hydrogen's unique properties, including lower density and viscosity. This assessment, using tools like computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations and pipeline flow modeling software, determines the pipeline's transport capacity and the pressure and temperature distribution. This information is vital for understanding how the pipeline will operate after re-qualification.

The introduction of a new fluid, such as hydrogen, can change the pipeline's transport capacity and loading conditions. Therefore, a flow assessment is necessary to determine these changes and establish the operational parameters for the re-qualified pipeline. This ensures the pipeline operates safely and efficiently.

The following scenarios are possible:

- Equal maximum velocity is integrity-wise the most conservative scenario at which maximum velocities in the grid will not change. In all other scenario's the velocity will need to increase with decreasing density. This scenario could be relevant if the grid has hard restrictions on increasing the velocity of gas.
- Equal pipeline capacity or equal capacity loss will provide the limit to which the current pipeline system can be used for hydrogen blending if the hydraulic capacity should stay the same. This means that during the transport cases comparing NG and hydrogen all pressure drops should stay the same.
- Equal energy flow is used to determine the impact of the transition assuming all clients have the same demand of energy as in the NG case, which is used as reference. This is a highly likely scenario when an existing grid starts to blend hydrogen, because all clients still require the same amount of energy (measured in MJ) for their application.

6.7 Step 7 – Safety and integrity reassessment

The pipeline system's safety and integrity must be reassessed based on the revised design basis. The risk register should be updated to reflect any new significant risks, including those related to up- and downstream connections. The risk assessment must ensure that changes are addressed in management and replacement plans. If parts of the pipeline are found non-compliant with updated integrity requirements, necessary modifications should be made. If modifications are deemed impractical or technically infeasible, revisiting operational parameters or considering a new pipeline might be necessary.

The revised design basis may introduce new failure modes and mechanisms. These should be identified and evaluated, including their causes and effects:

- Reduction in pipe steel material strength, toughness and ductility
- Reduction in critical defect sizes
- Increased fatigue damage and reduction in fatigue life
- Change in operational conditions and increase/decrease in pressure cycling (fatigue).
- Increase in gas velocity
- Change in design factor

When necessary, a gap-analysis should be performed to:

- Identify differences between the original and current design and construction standards
- Evaluate additional requirements that may be necessary, because of fluid-specific requirements or guidelines.

6.8 Step 8 – Identify modifications

Modifications and alternative solutions should be systematically identified and assessed for feasibility, safety, and structural integrity. The methodology for determining, evaluating, and implementing suitable modifications will depend on the specific outcomes desired. Risk mitigation can be achieved by minimizing the severity or potential consequences related to operational parameters such as pressure or other critical characteristics. Employing advanced instrumentation for enhanced control and monitoring of the system may also be necessary to address any newly identified risks. Additionally, retrospective materials testing may be required to ensure the continued reliability and performance of the system.

6.9 Step 9 – Documentation

To ensure transparency and regulatory compliance, the documentation of the system shall be performed continuously and systematically during all steps of the re-qualification process. This documentation, including drawings and operating procedures, is updated to reflect any modifications made to the system, ensuring a comprehensive record of changes. Key aspects and conclusions to be documented include:

- Current status of the system.
- Required status to transport the new fluid.
- Necessary system changes to achieve the required status.

The documentation shall be complete and reviewed by the end of this step.

6.10 Step 10 – Implementation

The implementation of changes to the pipeline system must precede the transition to hydrogen operation. This process involves executing the necessary modifications identified during re-qualification, ensuring compliance with established requirements, and updating maintenance and inspection plans to accommodate the unique properties of hydrogen. Additionally, it is crucial to provide comprehensive training for personnel to equip them with the skills and knowledge needed for hydrogen-related operations. Furthermore, risk-reducing measures, such as enhanced leak detection and mitigation strategies, must be implemented to ensure the safe and efficient repurposing of the pipeline system for hydrogen transportation.

When repurposing to hydrogen, it is crucial to understand its effects on pipeline integrity and propose actions to eliminate potential negative impacts. Various organizational areas will need to be updated, and new training for staff qualification will be required. Operational, maintenance, and inspection procedures, as well as contingency plans, must be revised due to hydrogen's unique flammability and explosiveness characteristics. The frequencies of maintenance and inspection plans, as well as the tools used, will likely need adjustment to meet the demands of the new fluid in the pipeline. Table 2 presents an overview of key areas to focus on to assure a safety implementation when repurposing a pipeline for hydrogen service.

Table 6– Areas to be focused on the company to be ready for hydrogen service

Organization and Personnel	Additional operations and maintenance staff Additional trainings
Operational and Maintenance	Update/develop operational procedures Update/ develop specifications
Contingency Plans	Emergency response planning Safety procedures
Risk Assessment and Integrity Management Planning	H2 associated risks need to be integrated into the exiting risk management process
Inspection and Monitoring	Inspection and maintenance plan/tools/frequency/limits/methodologies/technologies Monitoring of critical parameters such as pressure and pressure fluctuations Embrittlement and fatigue control Leak/fire detection

7 Conclusion

This report presents a 10-step protocol designed to assist offshore operators in assessing their pipelines for hydrogen repurposing.

Repurposing existing offshore pipelines for hydrogen transport presents both significant challenges and opportunities. While the infrastructure can offer a cost-effective solution, it requires a detailed assessment to evaluate its suitability, including the current condition of the pipeline, material compatibility with hydrogen, and the impact of hydrogen's properties on the pipeline over time. Available data on pipeline integrity, as well as comprehensive safety assessments, are essential to mitigate any risks associated with hydrogen transportation.

Furthermore, regulatory frameworks must be carefully considered, as current regulations may not fully address the unique challenges of hydrogen infrastructure. Ongoing development and updates in regulatory standards will be necessary to ensure the safe and effective integration of hydrogen into existing offshore pipeline networks.

Current hydrogen codes do not specifically address the unique requirements of offshore pipelines. To fill this gap, DNV is developing the recommended practice DNV RP-F123, which provides a technical framework for the design, construction, operation, and re-qualification of pipelines specifically for hydrogen transportation. This guideline has been developed based on DNV latest expertise in offshore pipelines and is designed to offer comprehensive requirements and best practices to ensure the safe and efficient operation of repurposed pipelines. It is aligned with the latest industry standards and recommended practices, such as those outlined in RP-F123, to provide a robust framework for the future of hydrogen infrastructure in offshore environments.

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Appendices

Appendix 1 ASME B31.12 material requirements

Table 7 – ASME B31.12 material requirements for option A and B [23]

Characteristic	Option A	Option B	Note
Charpy test	≤0°C or min. operating/pressure testing temperature, 27J full size (average)	Same as option A	1
Charpy base metal absorbed energy	$CVN = 0.008 \cdot (R \cdot T)^{0.39} \cdot \sigma_{hoop}^2$	Same as option A	2
Fracture shear %	At least 80% (average) for full size Charpy. At least 40% (average) for drop weight test (DWTT)	Same as option A	3
Fracture toughness & stress intensity (KIA and KIH)	Not addressed	KIH ≥ 55 MPa √m	4
Ultimate tensile strength	Max. 689 N/mm ² (100 ksi)	Max. 758 N/mm ² (110 ksi)	5
Yield strength	Max. 480 N/mm ² (70 ksi)	Max. 550 N/mm ² (80 ksi)	6
Steel composition and processing	Not addressed	P 0.015% max. Must be inclusion shape control.	7
Thickness	Not addressed	Repair and other activities may not reduce t to less than 87.5% of calculated nominal required wall thickness.	8
Design pressure limits	Not addressed	Limited to the greater of 85% of mill test pressure or field hydrotest pressure. Cold worked pipe subsequently heated has a reduced P to 75% of design pressure formula	9
Weld hardness	Max. 235 HV10	Same as option A	10

Notes:

1-2-3: Toughness requirement. Pipe should be of quality level API 5L PSL 2, meaning that the Charpy V toughness should be 27J (average of 3) for transverse Charpy test specimen. Requirement from specification is 47 J (above required 27 J) and is achieved during testing.

- Gas pipelines need to have adequate resistance to long running (brittle and ductile) fractures, so called crack arrest properties.
 - Brittle fracture control is to ensure the pipe has adequate ductility at operating temperature, normally tested with a Drop Weight Tear Test (DWTT).
 - Ductile fracture arrest control is to ensure that the pipeline has adequate toughness to arrest a ductile fracture when a fast-running ductile crack dissipates enough energy

to be arrested. B31.12 formulates required crack arrest properties that can be calculated with formula for minimum Charpy value CVN, see table above.

4: There are no fracture toughness testing requirements for API 5L that are comparable to the ASME B31.12 Option B requirements, and pipe mills are unlikely to have the ability to perform the required mechanical testing. It is likely that the pipeline operator would have to obtain pipe samples and have testing performed by a third-party service provider. ASME B31.12 does allow tests to be performed on pipe that is comparable to the project pipe.

5: The maximum allowable ultimate tensile strength is limited to 689 N/mm² (Option A) and to 758 N/mm² (Option B).

6: The maximum allowable ultimate tensile strength is limited to 480 N/mm² (Option A) and to 550 N/mm² (Option B).

7: Steel composition for option B: ASME B31.12 requires the max phosphorus (P) content of 0.015% when option B is used because of its possible embrittlement effect, which originated from sour (H₂S) gas specifications. The “inclusion shape control” requirement is usually not specified for the natural gas pipelines. This requirement is commonly used in the sour service meaning that HIC resistant steels should have minimum possible Sulphur (S) content (for sour service pipe should control S maximum 0.002%). Not meeting these requirement does not necessary mean that pipeline is not suitable for hydrogen service.

8: Requires at least “standard” wall thickness (ASME B36.10) for pipe ≤4” diameter and 6.4 mm for pipe > 4” diameter. The wall thickness tolerance is 12,5%.

9: This pressure limitation indicates that either the pre-service field hydrotest or the mill hydrotest would have to be at least 1.18 times the desired MAOP.

10: ASME B31.12 weld hardness requirement (235 HV₁₀), which is even more conservative than those found in sour service guidelines such as NACE MR0175/ ISO 15156. It is unlikely that the existing pipelines will meet this requirement. Older specifications for natural gas pipelines from the 1970s allowed a maximum hardness of 350 HV₁₀, reflecting the standards and materials knowledge of that time.

It shall be mentioned that in the new version of the EN 12732 [24] published in 2021, a max hardness requirement of 325 HV₁₀ has been set. This standard contains requirements for the production and testing of weld joints for the installation and modification, including in-service welding, of onshore steel pipelines and pipework used in gas infrastructure including non-conventional gases such as (injected) hydrogen. Thus, in European pipelines a less conservative hardness criterium can be considered.

Appendix 2 Materials testing

Table 8 – Tests to be performed when original materials certificates are unavailable

	Destructive	Non destructive
Toughness	Charpy ASTM E23 DWT ASTN E208	-
Fracture toughness & stress intensity (KIA and KIH)	See EPRG white paper [25]	-
Yield strength (YS) Ultimate tensile strength (UTS)	ASTM E8/E8M	ROMAT
Steel composition and processing	Chemical analysis, metallography	Spectrometry, replica
Wall Thickness	Metallography	Inline inspection
Weld hardness	ASTM E92	ASTM E3246, ASTM E110

Some explanations are provided below:

1. Toughness (Charpy +DWT)

To measure the toughness of a pipeline, the only feasible way is to cut out coupons from the pipeline and test them. To get reliable results, it is better to test at least three pipes, so that the variation the test results along the line can be evaluated. Impact tests shall be performed in parent metal, seam weld, girth weld metal and weld heat affected zone.

Standard Deviation (SD) of Charpy Toughness

The actual standard deviation of Charpy toughness's can only be estimated by taking several samples, testing them and calculating the SD from the outcomes. The number of tests performed affects how confidently the SD can be estimated, and how much conservatism is needed. Note that for steel with a low average Charpy, it is more conservative to assume a small SD rather than a large one, as this reduces the likelihood of a given pipe having enough toughness to stop a crack. However, this distribution has a high amount of variance, so that even with eight samples, the measured SD will need to be halved, and with six samples by a factor of two point five, to reach 95% confidence.

2. Option B requires measuring the threshold stress intensity factor (KIH) for the base material, weld metal, and heat-affected zone in both girth and seam welds. These measurements are necessary to demonstrate the materials' resistance to hydrogen embrittlement. It is usually obligatory for severe conditions and dynamic loading. Fracture toughness is normally not required to be tested for natural gas pipelines and therefore is not available. The pipeline material must undergo testing in a hydrogen environment to assess its specific properties under these conditions. This testing will also evaluate whether exposure to hydrogen affects the material by reducing its fracture toughness and altering the fatigue crack growth rates.

3. Pipeline steel properties: in case the pipeline properties are unknown

a) In-line Inspection Services for Material Verification

Determination of electromechanical parameters. The principle of this technique is that there is a relationship between the electrical conductivity and magnetic permeability with the mechanical properties of ferromagnetic materials. This technique is used by Rosen in a new type of MFL pig (ROMAT).

b) Destructive testing

In most cases, destructive testing is not desirable because a pipeline cannot or should not be taken out of service. In case some spare pipes are available, or material becomes available during repair or modification, it is possible to perform some standard tests to fill the company's material database. It is necessary to test parent metal, weld metal and seam weld specimens.

4. Chemical composition

When chemical composition is not known, some available methods are listed below:

- a) Using a spectrometer to find out the chemical composition (on spare pipe).
- b) The grain sizes of a material can be measured by making replicas and examining them under a microscope. A replica is a kind of image that shows the structure of the material. To make a replica, the piece of material is first cleaned (pickled). The replica can also reveal information about the heat treatment (higher strength can be achieved by extra heat treatments) as well as the grain size (on spare pipe).
5. Pipeline wall thickness: pipeline shall be piggable, or shall be made piggable, otherwise a hydrotest shall be performed to determine the MAOP and the current wt.

For a comprehensive inline inspection, utilizing both Magnetic Flux Leakage (MFL) and Electromagnetic Acoustic Transducer (EMAT) tools is advisable. MFL is highly effective in detecting metal loss, such as corrosion and pitting. However, MFL is limited in detecting certain types of crack-like defects. To complement MFL, the EMAT tool should be employed. EMAT is assumed to be suitable for identifying crack-like defects.

6. Weld hardness can be assessed using both destructive and non-destructive testing methods. Destructive testing, such as the Vickers or Rockwell hardness tests, involves creating an indentation in the weld, permanently altering the material. In contrast, non-destructive testing methods, like portable hardness testers, allow for hardness evaluation without damaging the weld, preserving its integrity for further use.

Appendix 3 Contaminations in existing offshore pipelines, [26]

This appendix describes some of the most common contaminants that can be found in upstream offshore natural gas pipelines, and their sources, effects, and mitigation methods. The information presented is based on a combination of literature review and in-house expertise. The contaminants include sulfur and H₂S, organo-halogens, solids and waxes, mercury and others. Each of these contaminants poses different challenges and risks for the pipeline integrity and safety. The following sections provide more details on each contaminant and its characteristics.

Sulfur and H₂S: Sulfur in oil and gas extraction primarily comes from the sulfur-containing compounds present in crude oil and natural gas reservoirs. These compounds include hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) and various organic sulfur compounds such as mercaptans, sulfides, and thiophenes.

During the extraction process, when natural gas is brought to the surface, these sulfur-containing compounds are also brought up. Hydrogen sulfide, in particular, is often found in natural gas deposits and can be released during drilling and production operations. Overall, sulfur in oil and gas extraction primarily originates from the sulfur compounds naturally present in the hydrocarbon reservoirs. These can vary from reservoir to reservoir and change over the lifetime of the field production. For example, reservoirs initially H₂S free, can start to produce H₂S later in life, especially if water injection or other enhanced recovery methods are used.

Possible Risks: contamination in natural gas production can introduce various risks, especially concerning safety, operational integrity, and environmental impact.

1. **Safety Concerns:** H₂S is highly toxic, even at low concentrations. Inhalation of H₂S gas can cause respiratory irritation, nausea, headaches, and in high concentrations, it can be fatal. Workers in oil and gas extraction facilities are at risk if proper safety measures are not in place to monitor and mitigate H₂S exposure.
2. **Corrosion:** H₂S can cause corrosion in pipelines, equipment, and infrastructure associated with natural gas production, processing, and transportation. This corrosion can weaken structures and lead to leaks or failures, posing safety hazards and causing costly damage.
3. **Environmental Impact:** Sulfur compounds, including H₂S, contribute to air pollution. When natural gas containing sulfur is burned for energy, it releases sulfur dioxide (SO₂) and other sulfur-containing compounds into the atmosphere, which can contribute to acid rain, smog formation, and adverse health effects.
4. **Regulatory Compliance:** Many jurisdictions have regulations limiting the amount of sulfur and H₂S allowed in natural gas. Gas producers must comply with these regulations to ensure the gas meets quality standards before it can be transported and sold.

Oxygen: In general, natural gas reservoirs are considered oxygen-free environments. This is primarily because natural gas formation occurs deep underground, typically in conditions where oxygen is scarce or absent.

1. **Formation Process:** Natural gas forms over millions of years from organic matter buried deep underground. The formation process involves the decomposition of organic material (such as plankton and algae) under high pressure and temperature conditions. This process occurs in sedimentary basins deep beneath the Earth's surface, where oxygen levels are extremely low or non-existent.
2. **Anaerobic Conditions:** The environment where natural gas forms is typically anaerobic, meaning it lacks oxygen. Anaerobic conditions are conducive to the preservation and transformation of organic matter into hydrocarbons like methane, which is the primary

component of natural gas. The absence of oxygen prevents the organic matter from fully oxidizing and instead allows it to undergo transformation into fossil fuels.

3. Migration and Entrapment: Once formed, natural gas migrates through porous rock formations until it becomes trapped beneath impermeable layers of rock, forming reservoirs. These reservoirs are often located deep underground, where oxygen does not penetrate due to the impermeability of the overlying rock layers.

While natural gas reservoirs are generally oxygen-free, it's important to note that trace amounts of oxygen may be present in some reservoirs due to geological processes or contamination. However, these levels are typically very low and not significant enough to support combustion or oxidation reactions within the reservoir. At a concentration level of 0.1%, oxygen is already problematic for various catalysts used in chemical processes.

Oxygen present in natural gas pipelines would therefore come from external sources. This is often from leaking pumps, valves, or from maintenance activities.

Possible Risks: The presence of oxygen in natural gas production can pose several risks, particularly in terms of safety, operational integrity, and environmental impact:

1. Fire and Explosion Hazard: Natural gas, which is primarily composed of methane, is highly flammable. If oxygen is introduced into a natural gas environment, it can create explosive mixtures that pose a significant fire and explosion hazard. Even small amounts of oxygen can increase the likelihood of combustion, especially in confined spaces or during handling and transportation processes.
2. Corrosion: Oxygen can promote corrosion in pipelines, equipment, and storage tanks used in natural gas production and transportation. Corrosion can weaken infrastructure, leading to leaks, failures, and potentially hazardous situations. Corrosion is particularly concerning in environments where moisture is present, as oxygen can react with water to form corrosive compounds.
3. Quality Control: Oxygen contamination can affect the quality of natural gas and its suitability for various applications. High levels of oxygen may impact the heating value of the gas, interfere with combustion processes, and cause operational issues in downstream equipment such as heaters, boilers, and engines.

Mercury: Mercury can be present in gas reservoirs as well as in associated formations and fluids.

Here are some sources of mercury in natural gas extraction:

1. Geological Formation: Mercury can naturally occur in geological formations where oil and gas are found. It may have been deposited along with sediments during the formation of the reservoir or introduced through volcanic activity or other geological processes.
2. Crude Oil and Natural Gas: Mercury can be present in crude oil and natural gas as trace contaminants. It can exist in various forms, including elemental mercury and mercury compounds. The concentration of mercury in oil and gas can vary depending on the source and geological characteristics of the reservoir.
3. Drilling Fluids and Additives: Some drilling fluids and additives used during the drilling process may contain mercury or mercury-containing compounds. These substances can come into contact with drilling equipment, fluids, and formations, potentially leading to mercury contamination in extracted oil and gas.
4. Formation Water: Water produced along with oil and gas (referred to as formation water or produced water) can contain dissolved or suspended mercury. Mercury may leach into

formation water from surrounding rock formations or from reservoir fluids during the extraction process.

Possible Risks: Mercury in natural gas production can pose several risks to human health, the environment, and industrial processes. Here are some of the key risks associated with mercury:

1. **Human Health Hazards:** Mercury is highly toxic, and exposure to even small amounts can have adverse health effects on humans. Inhalation of mercury vapors can cause respiratory problems, neurological disorders, and kidney damage. Workers in natural gas production facilities, as well as nearby communities, may be at risk of exposure if proper safety measures are not in place.
2. **Environmental Impact:** Mercury released into the environment can bioaccumulate in ecosystems, leading to contamination of soil, water, and wildlife. Once mercury enters the food chain, it can biomagnify, with concentrations increasing as it moves up through the food web. This can pose risks to aquatic organisms, birds, and mammals, including species consumed by humans.
3. **Corrosion and Equipment Damage:** Mercury can cause corrosion in pipelines, processing equipment, and storage tanks used in natural gas production and transportation. Corrosion can weaken infrastructure, leading to leaks, failures, and potential safety hazards. Mercury contamination can also damage sensitive equipment and instrumentation used in gas processing facilities.
4. **Operational Challenges:** Mercury contamination in natural gas can present operational challenges for gas processing and refining facilities. Mercury can interfere with process equipment, catalysts, and purification systems, reducing operational efficiency and increasing maintenance costs. It can also impact product quality and compliance with environmental regulations.

Organo-halogens: Organo-halogens, which are compounds containing carbon, hydrogen, and halogen atoms (such as fluorine, chlorine, bromine, or iodine), can be found in oil and gas extraction processes through various sources:

1. **Naturally Occurring Halogens:** Halogens are naturally occurring elements found in the Earth's crust and can be present in geological formations where oil and gas are extracted. Halogens may be released into the extracted fluids during drilling, production, and processing operations.
2. **Chemical Additives:** Organo-halogen compounds may be intentionally added to drilling fluids, completion fluids, and hydraulic fracturing fluids to improve performance or achieve specific objectives during oil and gas extraction. For example, certain biocides, corrosion inhibitors, and drilling mud additives may contain organo-halogens.
3. **By-products of Chemical Reactions:** Organo-halogens can be formed as byproducts of chemical reactions that occur during oil and gas production and processing. For example, chlorinated hydrocarbons may be formed during chlorination processes used for water treatment or as a result of reactions between hydrocarbons and chlorine-containing compounds.
4. **Microbial Activity:** Microbial communities present in oil and gas reservoirs and associated formations can also contribute to the production of organo-halogens through metabolic processes. For example, some microorganisms are capable of producing halogenated organic compounds as part of their metabolic pathways.

Possible Risks: The risks associated with organo-halogens in natural gas production can vary depending on the specific compounds involved and their concentrations. However, here are some general risks associated with organo-halogens in natural gas production:

1. **Environmental Impact:** Some organo-halogen compounds are persistent organic pollutants (POPs) that can bioaccumulate in the environment and pose risks to ecosystems and wildlife. These compounds can be toxic to aquatic organisms and may have long-term effects on biodiversity and ecosystem health.
2. **Human Health Hazards:** Exposure to certain organo-halogen compounds can pose health risks to workers in natural gas production facilities and nearby communities. Depending on the specific compounds involved, exposure may occur through inhalation, ingestion, or dermal contact. Health effects can range from respiratory irritation and skin sensitization to more serious effects such as neurotoxicity, reproductive toxicity, and carcinogenicity.
3. **Corrosion and Equipment Damage:** Some organo-halogen compounds can contribute to corrosion in pipelines, processing equipment, and storage tanks used in natural gas production and transportation. Corrosion can weaken infrastructure, leading to leaks, failures, and potential safety hazards. Additionally, organo-halogens may interact with other chemicals in the production process, leading to fouling or degradation of equipment and reducing operational efficiency.

Siloxanes: Siloxanes can enter natural gas processes from various sources, including:

1. **Natural Gas and Crude Oil Reservoirs:** Siloxanes can naturally occur in geological formations where oil and gas are found. These compounds may originate from the degradation of organic matter or geological processes involving silicon-containing minerals. Siloxanes can be present in reservoir fluids, including natural gas, crude oil, and associated formation water.
2. **Biological Processes:** Microbial activity in oil and gas reservoirs and associated formations can contribute to the production of siloxanes through metabolic processes. Some microorganisms are capable of synthesizing siloxane compounds as byproducts of their metabolism.
3. **Industrial Sources:** Siloxanes may also enter oil and gas extraction processes from industrial sources, including the use of silicone-based materials, products, and chemicals in drilling fluids, completion fluids, and hydraulic fracturing fluids. Silicone-based additives, lubricants, and sealants used in equipment and machinery maintenance may also contribute to siloxane contamination.
4. **Water Treatment Chemicals:** Siloxane compounds may be present in water treatment chemicals used in oil and gas production and processing facilities. Certain silicone-based antifoaming agents, emulsifiers, and demulsifiers used to treat produced water and wastewater may contain siloxanes.

Possible Risks: The risks associated with siloxanes in natural gas production primarily revolve around operational challenges, environmental impact, and potential health hazards. Here are some key risks:

1. **Operational Challenges:** Siloxanes can cause operational issues in natural gas processing facilities. When present in gas streams, siloxanes can condense and accumulate in processing equipment, pipelines, and heat exchangers. This can lead to fouling, corrosion, and reduced efficiency of equipment, resulting in increased maintenance costs and downtime.

2. **Environmental Impact:** Siloxanes can have adverse effects on the environment, particularly when released into the atmosphere. When natural gas containing siloxanes is burned for energy, siloxane combustion products, such as silicon dioxide (silica), may be emitted into the air. Silica particles can contribute to air pollution and respiratory problems if present in high concentrations. Additionally, siloxanes may contaminate soil and water if released into the environment.
3. **Health Hazards:** While siloxanes themselves are generally considered to have low toxicity, combustion of siloxanes can produce harmful byproducts, including fine particulate matter and other air pollutants. Prolonged exposure to these pollutants may pose health risks, particularly to individuals with respiratory conditions or compromised immune systems.
4. **Equipment Damage:** Siloxanes can contribute to corrosion and degradation of equipment and infrastructure in natural gas production and processing facilities. Corrosion caused by siloxanes can weaken pipelines, storage tanks, and processing equipment, leading to leaks, failures, and potential safety hazards.

Amines: Amines, particularly in the context of oil and gas extraction, often refer to amine compounds used in gas treatment processes, such as amine gas sweetening. These amines can come from:

1. **Synthetic Production:** Amines used in gas treatment processes are typically synthetic compounds manufactured specifically for this purpose. These amines are produced through chemical synthesis in industrial facilities. Commonly used amines in gas sweetening include monoethanolamine (MEA), diethanolamine (DEA), and methyldiethanolamine (MDEA).
2. **Gas Sweetening Process:** Amines are widely used in gas sweetening processes to remove acidic gases, particularly hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) and carbon dioxide (CO_2), from natural gas streams. In the gas sweetening process, the amine solution reacts with acidic gases to form stable compounds, which are then separated from the treated gas stream. This process helps to improve the quality of natural gas by reducing its sulfur and carbon dioxide content.
3. **Other Applications:** Various amines are used as corrosion inhibitors to protect pipelines and equipment from corrosion caused by acidic gases or water. Amines may also be used in drilling and completion fluids, as well as in enhanced oil recovery (EOR) processes.

Possible Risks: Amines used in natural gas treatment processes like gas sweetening, can pose various risks. Here are some potential risks associated with amines in natural gas production:

1. **Health Hazards:** Amines can be hazardous to human health, especially if workers are exposed to high concentrations or if proper safety measures are not in place. Exposure to amines through inhalation or skin contact can cause irritation to the respiratory system, skin, and eyes. Prolonged or repeated exposure to certain amines may lead to more serious health effects, including respiratory sensitization, allergic reactions, and systemic toxicity.
2. **Environmental Impact:** Amines and their degradation products can have environmental implications if released into the environment. For example, amines may be discharged into water bodies through wastewater from gas processing facilities, potentially affecting aquatic ecosystems. Additionally, amines may react with atmospheric pollutants to form secondary pollutants, contributing to air pollution and smog formation.
3. **Corrosion and Equipment Damage:** Certain amines are used for their corrosion inhibition properties. However, some concentrated amines and amine degradation products can contribute to corrosion in pipelines, processing equipment, and storage tanks if not properly managed. Corrosion can weaken infrastructure, leading to leaks, failures, and potential safety

hazards. Amines may also interact with other chemicals in the production process, leading to fouling or degradation of equipment and reducing operational efficiency.

Glycols: Glycols used in oil and gas production, particularly in dehydration processes, are typically synthetic compounds produced specifically for this purpose.

1. **Synthetic Production:** Glycols used in oil and gas extraction, such as ethylene glycol (EG) and diethylene glycol (DEG), are manufactured through chemical synthesis in industrial facilities. These glycols are produced from petrochemical feedstocks such as ethylene and ethylene oxide, which are derived from natural gas or petroleum sources.
2. **Dehydration Process:** Glycols are commonly used as desiccants in gas dehydration processes to remove water vapor from natural gas streams. In these processes, the glycol solution is circulated through a contactor tower where it absorbs water vapor from the gas stream. The dehydrated gas is then discharged, while the glycol-rich solution is regenerated for reuse.
3. **Other Applications:** Glycols have various other applications in oil and gas extraction beyond gas dehydration. For example, they are used as heat transfer fluids in heating and cooling systems, as well as in antifreeze formulations for equipment and pipelines. Glycols may also be used in drilling and completion fluids, as well as in hydraulic fracturing fluids.

Possible Risks: Glycols used in natural gas production, particularly in gas dehydration processes, can pose various risks to human health and, the environment.

1. **Health Hazards:** Exposure to certain glycols, particularly in their liquid or vapor form, can pose health risks to workers in natural gas production facilities. Inhalation or skin contact with glycols may cause irritation to the respiratory system, skin, and eyes. Prolonged or repeated exposure to glycols may lead to more serious health effects, including respiratory sensitization, allergic reactions, and systemic toxicity.
2. **Environmental Impact:** Glycols and their degradation products can have environmental implications if released into the environment. For example, glycols may be discharged into water bodies through wastewater from gas processing facilities, potentially affecting aquatic ecosystems. Additionally, glycols may volatilize into the atmosphere and contribute to air pollution if not properly contained or controlled.

Oil and Grease: Oil and grease in natural gas production typically originates from several sources within the production process:

1. **Equipment Lubricants:** Machinery and equipment used in natural gas extraction, such as pumps, compressors, valves, and rotating equipment, require lubrication to reduce friction and ensure smooth operation. Lubricating oils and greases are commonly used for this purpose. During operation, these lubricants can come into contact with natural gas or produced fluids and may become entrained in the extracted gas or liquid streams.
2. **Drilling and Production Fluids:** During drilling and production operations, various fluids are used to facilitate the extraction of oil and gas from underground reservoirs. These fluids may contain oil-based drilling muds, completion fluids, or hydraulic fracturing fluids, which can contain oils, greases, and other hydrocarbons. Residual oil and grease from these fluids may remain in the wellbore or be brought to the surface along with the extracted fluids.

3. **Formation Fluids:** Oil and grease can also be naturally present in the formation fluids produced along with natural gas. In some cases, oil reservoirs may contain associated natural gas, and during extraction, oil droplets may become suspended or entrained in the gas stream. Additionally, oil and grease may be present in produced water or condensate associated with natural gas production.
4. **Maintenance Activities:** Maintenance activities conducted at natural gas extraction facilities, such as equipment cleaning, degreasing, and maintenance of storage tanks and separators, may involve the use of oil-based cleaners, solvents, and degreasers.

Possible risks: The presence of oil and grease in natural gas production can pose various risks to human health, the environment, and operational integrity. Here are some potential risks associated with oil and grease in natural gas production:

1. **Environmental Contamination:** Oil and grease releases can lead to environmental contamination if they are spilled or leaked into the soil, water, or air during production, transportation, or storage activities. Oil and grease contamination can have detrimental effects on soil fertility, water quality, and aquatic ecosystems, impacting biodiversity and ecosystem health.
2. **Air Pollution:** Volatile components of oil and grease, such as hydrocarbons, can evaporate into the atmosphere and contribute to air pollution. When exposed to sunlight and atmospheric pollutants, volatile organic compounds (VOCs) emitted from oil and grease can react to form ground-level ozone, smog, and other air pollutants, which can have adverse effects on human health and the environment.
3. **Health Hazards:** Exposure to oil and grease, particularly through inhalation of vapours or direct skin contact, can pose health risks to workers in natural gas production facilities. Oil and grease may contain toxic chemicals, such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and heavy metals, which can cause respiratory problems, skin irritation, and other adverse health effects. Prolonged or repeated exposure to oil and grease may also increase the risk of chronic health conditions.
4. **Operational Challenges:** Oil and grease contamination can pose operational challenges in natural gas production facilities. Accumulation of oil and grease in equipment, pipelines, and processing units can lead to fouling, corrosion, and reduced operational efficiency. Maintenance costs may increase as a result of equipment damage and downtime caused by oil and grease-related issues.

Upstream production chemicals: Various chemical products can be used during natural gas production to manage various operational issues. The chemicals can be injected at various times and at different locations over the operational lifetime of an offshore natural gas facility. Possible products used in upstream natural gas production are:

1. **Corrosion Inhibitors:** Corrosion inhibitors are added to natural gas production systems to protect metal equipment, pipelines, and infrastructure from corrosion caused by acidic gases, water, and other corrosive substances present in the production environment.
2. **Scale Inhibitors:** Scale inhibitors are used to prevent the formation of scale deposits, such as calcium carbonate, calcium sulfate, and barium sulfate, which can accumulate in production equipment and pipelines and reduce operational efficiency.

3. **Biocides:** Biocides are chemicals used to control microbial growth and prevent the formation of biofilms in natural gas production systems. Microbial activity can lead to corrosion, fouling, and other operational issues if left unchecked.
4. **Surfactants:** Surfactants are surface-active agents that are added to drilling fluids, completion fluids, and hydraulic fracturing fluids to modify fluid properties, improve fluid performance, and enhance well productivity.
5. **Foaming Agents and Defoamers:** Foaming agents are used to generate stable foams in gas-liquid separation processes, such as gas dehydration and desalting, to increase surface area and improve separation efficiency. Defoamers are added to reduce foam formation and stabilize liquid levels in equipment.
6. **Demulsifiers:** Demulsifiers are chemicals used to break emulsions and separate water from oil and gas streams. Demulsifiers help improve the efficiency of water removal processes in production separators and dehydration units.
7. **Hydrate Inhibitors:** Hydrate inhibitors are added to natural gas streams to prevent the formation of gas hydrates, which can block pipelines and equipment and cause flow assurance problems during transportation and processing.
8. **Antifoaming Agents:** Antifoaming agents are used to control foam formation and reduce foam stability in various natural gas production processes, such as gas-liquid separation, dehydration, and desalting.
9. **Drag Reducing Agents:** Drag reducing agents (DRAs) are added to natural gas pipelines to reduce frictional resistance and increase flow rates, improving pipeline efficiency and reducing energy consumption.
10. **Emulsion Breakers:** Emulsion breakers are chemicals used to destabilize and break water-in-oil or oil-in-water emulsions, facilitating the separation of oil and water phases in production separators and treating equipment.
11. **Methanol:** Methanol is commonly injected into natural gas production systems to prevent hydrate formation.

Possible Risks: The presence of these chemicals or their residual products in natural gas production can pose various risks to human health, the environment, and operational integrity. Here are some potential risks associated with residual production chemicals in natural gas pipelines.

The use of chemicals in natural gas production can pose various risks to human health, the environment, and operational integrity. Here are some potential risks associated with the use of chemicals in natural gas production:

1. **Health Hazards:** Many chemicals used in natural gas production can be hazardous to human health if not properly handled, stored, or managed. Exposure to these chemicals through inhalation, skin contact, or ingestion can cause acute or chronic health effects, including respiratory irritation, skin sensitization, allergic reactions, neurological disorders, and carcinogenicity.
2. **Environmental Contamination:** Chemical releases or spills during handling, transportation, storage, or disposal can lead to environmental contamination of soil, water, and air.

Contamination may occur through surface runoff, groundwater infiltration, or atmospheric emissions, resulting in adverse effects on terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, wildlife, and human populations.

3. **Corrosion and Equipment Damage:** Some chemicals used in natural gas production, such as corrosion inhibitors and scale inhibitors, can contribute to corrosion or fouling of equipment, pipelines, and infrastructure if not properly applied especially in concentrated form. Corrosion and equipment damage can compromise operational integrity, increase maintenance costs, and pose safety hazards to workers and nearby communities.
4. **Biological Hazards:** Biocides used to control microbial growth in natural gas production systems can have unintended consequences, such as the development of biocide-resistant microorganisms or disruption of microbial ecosystems in soil and water environments. Excessive biocide use or improper application may lead to ecological imbalances and harm beneficial microorganisms.

Solids and fines: During natural gas production, various types of solid matter can be encountered, depending on the geological formation, production techniques, and operational processes involved. Some common types of solid matter encountered during natural gas production include:

1. **Sand and Sediments:** Sand and other sedimentary particles may be present in the formation fluids produced along with natural gas. These particles can enter the wellbore during drilling and production operations or may naturally occur in the reservoir. Sand and sediments can cause erosion and abrasion of equipment, reduce well productivity, and lead to sand production issues if not properly managed.
2. **Scale Deposits:** Scale deposits, such as calcium carbonate, calcium sulfate, and barium sulfate, can form in production equipment and pipelines due to the precipitation of dissolved minerals present in formation fluids. Scale formation can restrict flow rates, reduce production efficiency, and lead to equipment failure if not mitigated through scale inhibition and removal techniques.
3. **Formation Fines:** Formation fines are fine particles and clay minerals present in the reservoir rock that may become mobilized and produced along with natural gas. Formation fines can contribute to formation damage, reduce reservoir permeability, and impair well performance if not properly controlled or managed.
4. **Microbial Biomass:** Microbial biomass, including bacteria, fungi, and algae, may grow and proliferate in natural gas production systems, particularly in aqueous environments such as produced water or water injection systems. Microbial growth can lead to microbiologically influenced corrosion, biofouling, and souring issues if left unchecked.
5. **Sulfate-Reducing Bacteria (SRB):** SRBs produce sulfuric acid through their metabolic processes, which accelerates the corrosion of metal surfaces. This phenomenon, known as microbial-induced corrosion (MIC), is significantly influenced by SRBs, which are estimated to account for up to 80% of all MIC in natural environments.
6. **Asphaltenes:** Asphaltenes are high molecular weight organic compounds found in crude oil and natural gas condensate. During natural gas production, asphaltenes may precipitate and form solid deposits due to changes in temperature, pressure, and composition. Asphaltenes

deposition can cause fouling of production equipment, reduce well productivity, and lead to flow assurance issues in pipelines.

7. **Drilling Cuttings:** During drilling operations, solid cuttings, rock fragments, and drilling mud residues may accumulate in the wellbore and production tubing. Drilling cuttings can interfere with well productivity, hinder fluid flow, and require removal through well intervention or workover operations.
8. **Black Powder:** Black powder is a mixture of iron sulfides, iron oxides, and other contaminants like dirt, sand, and hydrocarbons. It is primarily formed due to the corrosion of the pipeline material, which reacts with contaminants such as hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), carbon dioxide (CO₂), and water.
9. **NORM (naturally occurring radioactive material):** NORM in pipelines typically originates from the geological formations where oil and gas are extracted. These formations contain naturally occurring radionuclides such as uranium, thorium, and their decay products, including radium-226 and radium-228. These radionuclides can dissolve in the produced water, a byproduct of oil and gas extraction.

Possible Risks: The presence of solids and fines in natural gas production can pose various risks to operational and mechanical integrity. Here are some potential risks associated with solids encountered during natural gas production:

1. **Equipment Damage:** Solid particles, such as sand, scale deposits, paraffin, and hydrates, can cause abrasion, erosion, and mechanical damage to production equipment, pipelines, valves, and other components. Equipment damage can lead to increased maintenance costs, production downtime, and safety hazards if not properly addressed.
2. **Flow Restriction:** Solid deposits, such as scale, sand and formation fines, can accumulate in production tubing, flowlines, and pipelines, causing flow restrictions and pressure losses. Flow restrictions can reduce production rates, impair well performance, and increase pumping requirements, resulting in decreased operational efficiency.
3. **Corrosion and Integrity Issues:** Solid deposits, microbial biomass, and other contaminants can promote corrosion and integrity issues in production equipment and infrastructure. Microbial activity, for example, can lead to microbiologically influenced corrosion (MIC), while scale deposits can create localized corrosion cells. Corrosion and integrity issues can compromise asset reliability, increase safety risks, and lead to environmental releases if left unaddressed. This is key risk for pipelines that have not been in active service for a period of time. Or may not have been properly laid up.
4. **Health and Safety Risks:** Solid matter in natural gas production systems can pose health and safety risks to workers, contractors, and nearby communities. Exposure to hazardous materials, such as drilling cuttings, scale, and chemicals, can lead to respiratory problems, skin irritation, and other adverse health effects. This is a key risk for solids that naturally radioactive (NORMs).

Appendix 4 Cleaning protocol [26]

This appendix describes in detail the proposed offshore pipeline cleaning process, following the high-level steps in the figure below.

Figure 6 – High-level offshore pipeline cleaning process

Pre-Assessment for contamination

Before proceeding to the physical cleaning stage, the first step is to conduct a pre-assessment of the particular offshore pipeline or section of pipeline to be readied for hydrogen service. The pre-assessment starts with a review of all existing records, analysis, and documentation on the history of the pipeline while it was in natural gas service. At a minimum, this review should include the following:

- Gas analysis, water analysis, pigging records, pigging debris analysis.
- Chemical treatment and corrosion management plans.
- Previous inspection results (ILI).
- Production history- changes in gas production, composition, volumes, water analyses, water dew point, hydrocarbon dewpoint.
- Pipeline suspension records – confirm how the pipeline operation was stopped and the current state of decommissioning.
- Operational history – verification of any modifications or repairs that would make pigging/cleaning challenging (change in wall thickness, tight bends, removal of pigging facilities, passing valves).
- Confirmation of pipeline pigging capability. Pig sender/receiver condition and condition of pigging/isolation valves at each end of the pipeline.
- Verification or absence of internal flow coating.

After the review and the quality/availability of the documentation, it will be necessary to perform an operational risk assessment. The scope and level of detail of the risk assessment will depend on the

level of uncertainty of the current condition with respect to contamination and the ability to be cleaned. If the documentation suggests the pipeline condition is not fully known, or there are gaps in the operational history, it is recommended to try to gather additional data. This could include gathering samples for analysis or site visits to confirm the current condition of pipeline isolation equipment.

It is strongly recommended that the operational risk assessment or HAZID be completed after the document review before proceeding to the pigging and cleaning stages. This assessment must consider.

- Side branches, dead legs and possible bypasses in associated piping.
- Valve isolation requirements and valve integrity assessment.
- Launcher/receiver integrity assessment or temporary pigging facilities.
- Sufficient working space for sending and receiving pigs and facilities to collect pigging debris.
- Contingency plans for stuck pigs.

Pipeline Pigging and Chemical Cleaning

Assuming the natural gas offshore pipeline is currently still in service and is equipped with facilities for pigging, pig the intended route during natural gas transport service with a BiDi (bidirectional) pig and monitor the amount of contamination carried (both the amount of liquids and the amount of solids). Repeat this step a few times until the contamination captured is less than 1-2 liters of solid/liquid (depending on the pipe diameter: 1 liter for up to 12 inches; above that, 2 liters).

If the pipeline is not in active service, the pre-assessment review and risk assessment must estimate the current condition of the pipeline.

If the current condition is known, the pipeline can be pigged same as above with a BiDi pig pushed with high pressure nitrogen. Typically, the pipeline would be pigged from the offshore to onshore direction.

If the current condition is not known due to incomplete records, then then the pipeline should be cleaned using a progressive pigging strategy. Progressive pigging consists of a series of pigging operations, starting with inefficient sealing pigs moving up to more aggressive and efficient pigs as confidence grows. The goal of this strategy is to reduce the chance of a stuck pig or creating a pile of debris in the pipeline ahead of the pig. The time and cost of multiple pig runs is typically less than the time and effort required to remove a stuck pig from a pipeline, especially an offshore pipeline.

In progressive pigging, the first pigs to be run are made from soft foam material, non-aggressive pigs, that can prove the pipeline can be successfully pigged and will sweep soft loose material and some liquids. Depending on the amount and nature of the contamination, these pigs can be increased in hardness, aggressiveness (brushes) and diameter. These pigs will remove solids and liquids until the pipeline becomes clean. The number of pig runs will depend on how much material is in the line.

It is expected that for almost all cases of natural gas service, BiDi pigging or a progressive pigging program with a few runs will be sufficient to meet the target cleanliness requirements, which can be found below:

- For pipelines <12 inch (DN 300) less than 1L of liquid/solids
- For pipelines >12 inch (DN 300) less than 2L of liquid/solids
- Hydrocarbons; maximum 1000 ppm

- Water dewpoint < -8°C @ 70 bar.

If the progressive pigging program is not effective, there is an option to supplement the pigging with a chemical cleaning program. This is only recommended if the progressive pigging program cannot deliver the cleanliness requirements.

The chemical cleaning program is typically carried out by specialist contractors in conjunction with chemical solution providers. The chemicals used in the cleaning operation are typically chosen by analysis of the debris coming from the pipeline. Laboratory testing can be used to help select the most effective chemical treatment. Options available are:

- Hydrocarbon solvents such as diesel, xylene, toluene, etc.
- Or specialist pipeline cleaning products such as N-SPEC [27]

Regardless of the chemicals used, they will need to be removed after by additional pigging pushed with nitrogen. No chemical residue must be left in the pipeline after cleaning. Also, any chemicals used offshore for cleaning should meet the OSPAR requirements [28].

Displace natural gas with nitrogen

This step entails displacing natural gas with nitrogen using a pig-run and preserving the pipeline under a low-pressure nitrogen atmosphere. After pigging, displace any natural gas with nitrogen and use a separating pig. The nitrogen quality should be monitored at the end of the pipeline for hydrocarbon content and water dew point. Below is an example of a pipeline purge with nitrogen showing how the contamination can reduce as the nitrogen purge progresses.

Figure 7 – Total hydrocarbon and water dewpoint at pipeline exit during purge with nitrogen [14]

The pipeline should be left under a nitrogen pressure of 2-3 bar overpressure. The hydrocarbon concentrations in the nitrogen should be monitored for a bi-weekly period (which indicates the extent to which volatile components are still present in the pipe section that are released at low pressure). In the event of persistent increases in concentrations of hydrocarbons above 0.1 % by volume, an

additional nitrogen purge must be carried out. During this phase, also check the mercury levels (as far as detectable at ng/m³ level).

Repairs and Modifications

This step includes a modification period under low-pressure nitrogen atmosphere. If required, maintenance/replacement of valves should be carried out. Caps should be placed on branches that are no longer operational, etc. Concentrations of volatile components (including hydrocarbons and mercury) in the nitrogen atmosphere due to desorption from pipe components should be monitored.

The pipeline section should be disconnected from the natural gas transport network to eliminate the risk of future cross-contamination. The connecting valves between the pipe section and other parts containing natural gas should be closed. Isolation on the basis of a single valve is not permitted. The complete physical separation of the hydrogen network from the natural gas network is essential in this regard. Mechanical jobs, i.e. work on valves, branches, etc. can then be carried out.

Cleaning Pigs with Nitrogen

The next step involves cleaning with a pig-run under a nitrogen atmosphere. Monitoring of contaminants in hydrogen (e.g. nitrogen, hydrocarbons and mercury) should be conducted and also testing with criteria. In case of rejection, the pipe should be purged again with nitrogen.

A cleaning pig-run using a BiDi (bi-directional) pig should be performed under nitrogen while monitoring the contamination found. Depending on the contamination found (welding grains etc. or whether liquids have also come with it), an extra pig-run should be performed if necessary until the pig is found dry and clean in the receiver. If the pig still brings a lot of greasy substances, a methanol run (approx. 20 m³ to be specified on the basis of pipe diameters) between pigs can be considered but be aware that even a methanol run will not be able to completely clean dead legs. During a methanol run, one should check for the volume of methanol deployed at the launcher and recovered volume at the receiver. After a methanol run, siphons should be emptied and valves should be drained. It is recommended to wait to transfer hydrogen until a pipeline section involved can become part of an operational hydrogen network (i.e. allow residual volatile components from the natural gas operation phase to evaporate into the nitrogen for as long as possible monitoring phase, preventing them from contaminating the hydrogen in the initial phase).

Displace Nitrogen with Hydrogen

This step involves the displacement of nitrogen to hydrogen using a pig-run. Hydrogen should be introduced into the network with a BiDi-pig as a separation between the gases (if desired, consider using a second pig (50-100 m distance between the pigs) to limit potential back-mixing (this also limits the influence of branches that are considered dead ends). Perform this at a hydrogen pressure of approximately 5 -10 bar. Hydrogen pressure can then be increased to the operational value and operation of the network can continue.

Appendix 5: Safety Related Properties of Hydrogen

Some safety-related hydrogen properties require special attention. They include its low density, low ignition energy, wide flammability range, and potential explosiveness. Table 9 summarizes hydrogen parameters that can influence safety and compares them with those for methane. For each parameter, the impact on safety is described. For completeness, this table also includes parameters that are relatively similar to methane.

Table 9 – Comparison of Methane and Hydrogen Safety Related Properties

Property	Hydrogen	Methane	Consequences for Hydrogen Safety
Gas density at NTP (kg/m³)	0.0827	0.659	Can be positive for outdoor dispersion due to buoyancy, but only for passive clouds. High-pressure jet dispersion is dominated by momentum not buoyancy. Also, negative because LFL may extend further for hydrogen jet than for methane.
Flammability range (25°C,101.3kPa) (vol%)	4 to 75	5 to 17	Negative, causing larger flammable cloud volumes. LFL = 4% only for upward propagating H ₂ flames, 8% is the lean limit of hydrogen combustion for practical applications.
Auto Ignition Temperature (°C)	585	537	Neutral
Minimum ignition energy (mJ)	0.017	0.27	Negative. The ignition energy for hydrogen varies significantly with gas concentration. For hydrogen concentrations up to 15%, the ignition energy is less than that of methane, with the absolute minimum for hydrogen being more than an order of magnitude less than for methane.
Boiling point (°C)	-253	-161	More challenging than methane. Liquid hydrogen can condense oxygen in air and cause unknown effects due to concentrated oxygen. Cryogenic effects different from LNG. Of no consequence for gas pipelines.
Heat of combustion (kJ/g)	120	50	For high-pressure gas releases at the same pressure and through the same hole size, the energy released for hydrogen is about 85% of that for methane.
Maximum burning velocity (cm/s)	265 to 325	37 to 45	Negative. Results in much greater flame acceleration in congested areas and higher pressures in confined spaces due to the greater difficulty in venting the explosion fast enough. Rapid flame acceleration will give high explosion pressures in small clouds.
Detonability measured in minimum mass of tetryl (Bull, 1979) (g)	0.8	16,000	Negative. Given greater flame acceleration with hydrogen (see above), DDT is a realistic if unlikely possibility even without congestion. This is not the case for methane. A hydrogen detonation can propagate through the full cloud and increase the explosion overpressure severity significantly.
Laminar diffusion coefficient at NTP (cm²/s)	0.61	0.16	Negligible effect on dispersion which is dominated by turbulent diffusion. Other effects are more important, such as flow speed and low hydrogen density causing longer momentum jets.

Speed of sound at NTP (m/s)	1294	446	Negative. Contributes to larger volumetric flowrates from leaks. Hydrogen has higher speed of sound and lower density. These largely cancel each other out, resulting in similar jet momentum for releases with the same pressure and hole size.
Joule-Thomson effect when pressure is relieved	Causes a small temperature increase	Causes a temperature decrease	Negligible since the temperature increase effect on hydrogen is only a few Kelvins. Requirement to limit CH ₂ temperature in storage tanks restricts filling rates (relevant for CH ₂ bunkering).
Adiabatic flame temperature (°C)	2045	1875	Negative. Hydrogen flames can burn hotter than methane. Likely to speed up escalation to other equipment and structures. Will have a negative impact on existing passive fire protection on structures and equipment.
Heat radiated from flame to surroundings (%)	17 to 25	23 to 33	These ranges are indicative and vary with release rate. Smaller hydrogen flames are invisible. At large release rates, a hydrogen fire can have the same radiation level as methane. There is very limited largescale hydrogen data available.

Appendix 6: Failure frequency hydrogen pipelines considerations

Hydrogen embrittlement is a degradation of the steel of the pipeline due to the presence of hydrogen. The only relevant form of hydrogen embrittlement for carbon steel is fatigue crack growth [29]. Fatigue crack growth can be managed by controlling the pressure swings that occur in the pipeline. As the crack growth rate is well known and generally the number and size of pressure swings in offshore pipelines are reasonably low, it is, therefore, assumed that subsea hydrogen pipelines will not fail due to hydrogen embrittlement.

Published work by Gasunie [30] and the UK HSE [31] support using same rupture frequencies as natural gas for onshore pipelines repurposed for operation with hydrogen, if pressure cycling (potentially causing higher fatigue rates) is avoided. The repurposing of offshore subsea pipelines and risers from natural gas usage to hydrogen should follow the same internal failure mechanisms as onshore pipelines, the main difference being external corrosion and interference i.e. anchor drag, effects of scour etc. These will remain constant for subsea pipelines regardless of the material transported.

However, there is uncertainty around the long-term effects of hydrogen especially for repurposed natural gas pipelines, and there is substantial ongoing research into the effects of hydrogen transportation on materials, including investigating the effects of hydrogen on girth welds and the behaviour of the pipeline material in a hydrogen environment following external interference (e.g. dent or dent-gouge from anchor drag). Also, the behaviour for a defect that occurred in natural gas service prior to being repurposed to hydrogen vs a defect that occurs in hydrogen service may be different.

Appendix 7: Hydrogen Release Rate

The majority of offshore subsea pipelines operate at above 1.8bar so any natural gas or hydrogen release will be sonic and choked flow will occur at the failure point.

Given choked outflow and the same source condition (source pressure, temperature and hole size) the mass flow rate for methane and typical natural gas is 2.8 and 3.2 times higher than for hydrogen respectively [32]. As the ratio of the densities of methane to hydrogen is approximately 8, the volumetric release rate of hydrogen is about by $8 / 2.8 = 2.9$ more than that of methane. As the orifice size is a constant, the initial hydrogen gas velocities will also be higher by this factor. The momentum (mass flow rate x gas velocity) of the gas as it is released is therefore essentially the same for hydrogen and methane releases. For long pipelines where there is no isolation between the installation riser ESDV and the landfall ESDV the release rate from small failures will be constant and approximately 3 times lower mass flowrate than for an equivalent natural gas release from the same failure. Where there is a subsea isolation valve (SSIV) by the installation that can be remotely activated the time dependent behaviour for a release of a fixed inventory of gas is more complex. As an example, comparison for the outflow of methane and hydrogen gas from a 95m length of 24" pipe (pipeline volume 27.4m³) through a 20mm diameter hole, with an initial pressure and temperature of 150bara and 285K respectively is examined.

Figure 8 shows the time dependent properties as the contents of the isolated section of subsea pipeline are released, shown once isolation has been made.

Figure 8 – Pipeline and release properties for hydrogen and methane (mass release rate – top left, volumetric flow – top right, vessel pressure – bottom left and release momentum – bottom right)

As discussed above, the ratio of the initial mass flow rates of methane and hydrogen is 2.8:1. However, as the release progresses, this ratio increases, being about 10:1 after about 6 minutes and then continues to rise further (Figure 8 – top left). This rise happens because the volumetric flow of hydrogen is higher than for methane (Figure 8 – top right) and the pressure in the isolated section of the pipeline therefore falls much quicker for hydrogen compared to methane (Figure 8 – bottom left). The consequence of this is that though the initial release momentum is about the same, the hydrogen case decays much faster than the methane case (Figure 8 – bottom right) and the release conditions will deviate more as time progresses.

Thus, for the same system pressure, volume between riser ESDV and pipeline SSIV and orifice size, the representative duration of a hydrogen jet fire will be nearly a third of that of a methane jet fire once isolation of the pressurised system has been achieved.

Figure 9 shows a comparison of release rates for 50,100 and 150barg for hole sizes between 1 and 1000mm for long pipelines and risers containing very large inventories of hydrogen at pressures above 1.8 bara and 10°C (DNV, Phast Version 9.0). It is evident that for the same hole size and pressure the mass release rate of methane is higher than for hydrogen. Note that the methane release rates at 50barg are almost identical to the hydrogen rates at 150barg. The release rate through a known failure size (diameter) can be estimated using the curves shown in Figure 9 or by using the formulae below:
 Hydrogen Release Rate [kg/s] = $(4.1 \times 10^{-5} \times \text{Pressure [Barg]} + 1.66 \times 10^{-4}) \times (\text{Hole Size [mm]})^2$

Figure 9 – Comparison of Methane and Hydrogen Release Rates at 50, 100 and 150 barg

Energy Release – Comparison Methane and Hydrogen

The heat of combustion, not including the latent heat produced by water vapour condensation, of methane and hydrogen is 50 MJ/kg and 120 MJ/kg respectively. The power of a jet fire is given by:
 $Power [MJ] = mass\ flow\ rate [kg/s] \times heat\ of\ combustion [MJ/kg]$

Multiplying the higher mass flow rate of the methane release by the lower heat of combustion, provides an outflow power that is quite similar to that of hydrogen – the outflow power of hydrogen being about 85% of the methane power. The combustion energy available from a hydrogen release is therefore slightly less than that from a methane release under the same release conditions. The ratio between hydrogen and natural gas could vary slightly from the 0.85 factor for methane given that higher hydrocarbons give about 5% less heat of combustion compared to methane and there will also be inert gases present. Though the initial powers are similar, for the transient release assessed in the previous section, the hydrogen power decreases much quicker than the methane case.

Figure 10 – Comparison of methane and hydrogen release power variation with time

Effect of water depth on release rate

The head of sea water above the pipeline/riser release point reduces the effective release pressure which in turn leads to a lower hydrogen release rate. The pressure head (Pa) of sea water acting on the pipeline/riser is equal to the product of the sea water density (1023.6 kg/m³), gravity (9.81m/s²) and sea depth in meters. The equation below can be used to estimate the effective pressure at any sea depth: *Effective Release Pressure [Barg] = Pipeline Pressure [Barg] - (1023.6 x 9.81 x Sea Depth [m] / 1x 10⁵)*

The maximum depth of the North Sea in the Dutch sector is ~70m, the head of sea water at the sea floor is equivalent to 7bar, so a release from a pipeline with internal pressure of 100barg would have an effective release pressure of 93barg.

Estimation of Sea Surface Bubble Zone Diameter

As a gas release rises to the sea surface it expands and the area of bubbles increases proportionately to the release rate and the depth. The extent of the bubble zone diameter is limited by the sea depth so as the rate increases the bubble zone diameter reaches a constant. DNV’s PlumePro software has been used to estimate the sea surface bubble zone diameter for sea depths between 10m and 70m and hydrogen release rates of 1kg/s to 3000kg/s. Figure below shows the relationship between release rate and bubble zone diameter for pipelines/riser failures at different sea depths.

Figure 11 – Hydrogen Release Rate versus Bubble Zone Diameter for Different Sea Depths

DNV PlumePro assumes methane is the gas released. Hydrogen has a slightly greater buoyancy than methane because the difference between the density of water and hydrogen is larger than the

difference between the density of water and methane. However, the differences in relative buoyancies between methane and hydrogen are extremely small at less than 0.1% so DNV PlumePro is suitable for estimating bubble zone diameters for hydrogen.

Atmospheric Dispersion of Subsea Releases

The bubble zone diameter provides an estimate of the where streams of hydrogen bubbles / flow can be present at the sea surface. It is unlikely that the hydrogen will be evenly distributed across the area of the bubble zone, and it is likely that some parts of the bubble zone will have significantly more hydrogen flowing from it than others. However, for dispersion modelling using PHAST it has been assumed that the flow through the bubble area is uniform and the pressure of the hydrogen at the sea surface is just above atmospheric pressure (1-2 Pa).

The figures below show a comparison of large natural gas and hydrogen dispersion from a 24-inch subsea pipeline. The pipeline pressure is 100barg and is at a depth of 30m. The bubble zone diameters for both release cases are 48m. The pipeline failure hole size has been adjusted to give a release rate of 1500kg/s of gas; 320mm diameter for natural gas and 600mm for hydrogen. Figure 12 shows the dispersion of natural gas to LFL in 2F and 10D weather conditions. Figure 13 shows the dispersion of hydrogen to LFL and 10% (extent of flammable mass for use in fire calculations) in 2F and 10D weather.

Figure 12 – Subsea Pipeline Natural Gas Release Fixed Mass- Above Sea Surface Dispersion

Figure 13 – Subsea Pipeline Hydrogen Release Fixed Mass – Above Sea Surface Dispersion

In calm conditions (2F) the natural gas LFL extends downwind 720m and has a maximum height of 125m. For hydrogen in 2F weather, the 10% concentration extends to 1170m and reaches a maximum height of 150m. In typical southern North Sea conditions (10D) the natural gas LFL extends downwind 170m and has a maximum height of 45m. For hydrogen in 10D weather, the 10% concentration extends 200m and has a maximum height of 210m. In both weather conditions the dispersion distances and height of the flammable portion of the hydrogen are greater than that for natural gas given the same release rate.

The figures below show a comparison of large natural gas and hydrogen dispersion from a 24-inch subsea pipeline. The pipeline pressure is 100barg and is at a depth of 30m. The bubble zone diameters for both release cases are 48m. The pipeline hole size is 400mm for both cases; this results in a release rate of 2342kg/s of natural gas and 666kg/s of hydrogen. Figure 14 shows the dispersion of natural gas to LFL in 2F and 10D weather conditions. Figure 15 shows the dispersion of hydrogen to LFL and 10% (extent of flammable mass for use in fire calculations) in 2F and 10D weather.

Figure 14 – Subsea Pipeline Natural Gas Release Fixed Hole Size - Above Sea Surface Dispersion

Figure 15 – Subsea Pipeline Hydrogen Release Fixed Hole Size – Above Sea Surface Dispersion

In calm conditions (2F) the natural gas LFL extends downwind 1000m and has a maximum height of 130m. For hydrogen in 2F weather, the 10% concentration extends to 740m and reaches a maximum height of 130m. In typical southern North Sea conditions (10D) the natural gas LFL extends downwind 210m and has a maximum height of 56m. For hydrogen in 10D weather, the 10% concentration extends

140m and has a maximum height of 88m. For gas releases from the same diameter the flammable portion of natural gas disperses further than hydrogen, but the maximum height reached is lower.

Figures 16 to 19 show hydrogen dispersion to LFL and 10% in 2F and D10 for different subsea pipeline release rates at sea depth of 30m: 10kg/s, 100kg/s, 500kg/s and 3000kg/s.

Figure 16 – 10kg/s Subsea Hydrogen Release in 30m Sea Depth

Figure 17 – 100kg/s Subsea Hydrogen Release in 30m Sea Depth

Figure 18 – 500kg/s Subsea Hydrogen Release in 30m Sea Depth

Figure 19 – 3000kg/s Subsea Hydrogen Release in 30m Sea Depth

Sea Surface Fires

For a sea surface fire to occur there needs to be ignition and the hydrogen supply rate per unit area needs to be above the burn velocity i.e. the fuel must be supplied at the burn rate or higher to sustain a flame at the sea surface. Ignition can come from either a local source at the sea surface such as a supply vessel or access vessel or could occur if a cloud ignites on the installation and burns back to the sea surface. The minimum laminar burn rate for 75% hydrogen in air (just flammable as air starts to dilute the hydrogen) is 0.5m/s. As such a mixture has a density of 0.419kg/s, the approximate minimum burn velocity at the sea surface is 0.21kg/m²s.

Because it is unlikely the gas is released uniformly through the bubble zone it is difficult to estimate the size of any sea surface pool fire. Table 10 shows the percentage of the bubble zone area that is required to be occupied by the subsea gas flow to sustain a stable flame. As an example, a 50kg/s release at a depth of 30m could sustain a sea fire of 13% of the bubble zone caused by the spreading of the release, if the flow was spread uniformly across the bubble zone a stable flame would not form. Whereas a 400kg/s release at a depth of 30m could sustain a sea surface fire across the whole bubble zone (100%). The deeper the release the larger the bubble zone and the smaller the sustainable percentage becomes for any given release rate. The smaller the percentage the lower the likelihood of a stable fire forming given ignition.

Table 10 – Mass Release rate vs Percentage of bubble zone area capable of sustaining hydrogen fire

Mass Release Rate (kg/s)	Percentage of bubble zone area capable of sustaining hydrogen fire (%)						
	10m Sea Depth	20m Sea Depth	30m Sea Depth	40m Sea Depth	50m Sea Depth	60m Sea Depth	70m Sea Depth
1	6%	1.3%	0.6%	0.4%	0.3%	0.2%	0.2%
5	15%	4%	2%	1.4%	1.1%	0.9%	0.7%
10	24%	6%	3%	2%	1.3%	1.3%	1.3%
50	100%	30%	13%	10%	8%	7%	7%
100	100%	59%	26%	21%	16%	13%	13%
200	100%	100%	53%	42%	32%	26%	26%
300	100%	100%	79%	62%	47%	39%	39%
400	100%	100%	100%	77%	59%	47%	47%
500	100%	100%	100%	90%	70%	53%	39%
1000	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	72%	72%
2000	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
3000	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Sea Fire Flame Lengths

Should ignition of the subsea hydrogen release occur at the sea surface the flammable portion of the hydrogen gas cloud will burn. The fire will have low momentum as the hydrogen pressure at the sea surface is extremely low. The flame shape will largely follow that of the dispersions shown above. For flames in F2 and D10 weather the flame length will increase as the release rate increases. For the same mass release rates, the hydrogen flames are larger than the natural gas flames.

Figure 20 shows approximate flame lengths for the hydrogen subsea releases from the 24-inch pipeline at 100barg at 30m depth compared to similar release rates of natural gas.

Figure 20 – Comparison of Hydrogen and Natural Gas Sea Surface Fire Flame Lengths

Vulnerability Criteria Escalation

The criteria for assessing vulnerability of people and assets to thermal radiation and explosion overpressure for consequences of hydrogen pipeline/riser failures should be the same as those used for natural gas events.

Escalation and Domino Effect

The criteria for assessing escalation of an initial hydrogen pipeline failure to a secondary event either at the landfall site or the installation should follow the same rulesets as those developed for natural gas escalation. The modelling of hydrogen events may yield more severe consequences, e.g., significantly higher explosion overpressures due to the potential for detonation and higher flame temperatures which may fail passive fire protection quickly. Overall, the potential for escalation is higher for hydrogen pipeline failures particularly where there is congestion and uncontrolled ignition sources (e.g. coastal area of landfall site).

NEN 3656_2022 section 6.7.1 requires the potential for domino effect at the landfall site to be assessed. This is important where the pipelines come ashore in industrial areas and a failure may result in:

- Flammable clouds of hydrogen drifting into neighbouring industrial complexes, where they could ignite and cause damage and escalation from high levels of radiation and overpressure.
- Thermal events (jet fires) at the hydrogen pipeline causing high levels of radiation at or inside a neighbouring industrial site.

A large pipeline/riser failure offshore could damage adjacent pipelines and or risers, cables or umbilicals in the near vicinity or cause a hazard at the sea surface to ships in busy shipping lanes.